

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

**THE POTENTIAL OF MATCHA IN REDUCING
COFFEE DEPENDENCE: KEY FACTORS AMONG
COLLEGE STUDENTS AT SSC-R MANILA**

A Research Proposal
Presented to the College Department
San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration
Major in Legal Management

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May 2025

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

For many college students, coffee has become an important part of their daily routine. It is assumed that drinking coffee is a way of staying awake during long periods of work or study sessions, but for some, it is almost an absolute necessity in order to function throughout the day. The main component of coffee, caffeine, is primarily responsible for its stimulating effects that help us feel awake and alert. Among the most common sources of caffeine are coffee and energy drinks. Recently, matcha has also emerged as another energy source. Although both coffee and matcha are known for their energy-boosting properties, students may experience them in different ways.

According to MacDonnell (2024), experts predict that by 2025, Filipinos consume an average of 3.78 kilograms of coffee per person from 3.05 kilograms in 2021. This shows that caffeine is one of the most widely used stimulants by students and workers who aim to stay alert and focused. However, it can lead to dependence if consumed regularly in large amounts. While coffee has been the preferred choice for many years, there is a noticeable demand for alternative drinks that provide similar benefits but with fewer side effects.

Matcha, a powdered form of green tea, has already emerged as a popular energy source worldwide, well before studies at San Sebastian College - Recoletos Manila. In 2022, the global matcha market was valued at USD 4.11 billion and is projected to grow to USD 6.83 billion by 2030, with an annual growth rate of 8.95%. This growth reflects a rising consumer trend driven by matcha's unique combination of caffeine and L-theanine, which provides a stable,

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focused energy boost without the jitteriness often associated with coffee. Studies have shown that matcha enhances cognitive function while promoting relaxation, making it an attractive, healthier alternative for students managing academic stress. The interest in exploring matcha as a healthier energy option at San Sebastian College primarily comes from the researchers, motivated by the potential benefits for students who rely on coffee.

Given these factors, this study aims to explore not only the perceptions of SSC-R Manila students regarding matcha compared to coffee but also their current consumption patterns and willingness to switch from coffee to matcha. The researchers also aim to identify potential business opportunities for SSCR Manila, such as developing new product lines, optimizing marketing strategies, and improving operational efficiency.

Additionally, this paper intends to add clarity to the feasibility and marketability of matcha as an alternative by adding the necessary literature to this emerging topic related to one of the most consumed commodities in history (Grand View Research, 2023). With the global matcha market projected to grow significantly, driven by increasing health consciousness and demand for natural products, understanding student perceptions and consumption patterns can provide insights into whether matcha could effectively replace or complement traditional coffee in the students' daily routines.

Review of Related Literature

This part provides a review of related literature regarding caffeine consumption and its effects, particularly among students. It shows that while caffeine can help students stay awake and focus, it can also cause stress and

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problems with sleeping which is also vital for the well-being of every student. The following review also looks at various factors influencing caffeine use, including personal preferences, academic pressures, and the potential risks of overconsumption. Understanding this section of the paper is essential as it provides information that could turn into an entry point for business opportunities such as introducing matcha as a substitute to coffee.

According to Viado (2024), coffee consumption is perceived to significantly improve their cognitive functions, such as memory retention and thinking abilities. Some of the students feel stressed when drinking coffee which affects their motivation to complete their school tasks. The findings of their study aligns more closely with the objectives of this paper as it offers direct comparison to the negative effects of coffee consumption. However, it does not fully address the potential of alternative beverages like matcha.

Based on the paper of Bautista (2022), the study identified several important factors affecting caffeine consumption, sleep quality, and motivation. Students consume a variety of caffeinated beverages at different times and frequencies. Different demographic groups are driven by distinct factors in their choice of caffeinated drinks. Sleep quality among respondents is generally moderate to poor, with notable differences between genders, but sleep quality does not significantly affect caffeine consumption. While the findings of the study shows why students consume caffeine and how it relates to their quality of sleep, it does not directly address how healthier options, like matcha, might affect students' sleep patterns or energy levels in a way that could be more beneficial than coffee.

According to Sokary et al. (2022), their review highlights the numerous benefits of matcha, including its ability to enhance attention and memory, which are crucial aspects of cognitive function. Additionally, matcha helps reduce stress

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and has no negative impact on mood. The review's findings are relevant as they suggested that matcha could offer healthier and more balanced options for students looking to boost their focus and manage stress, without the potential downsides of coffee.

In a separate study by Mahoney et al. (2019), shows that ninety-two (92%) of students reported consuming caffeine in any form within the previous year. Students listed a variety of motivations for using caffeine, such as feeling awake (79%); enjoy the flavor (68%); the social aspects of consumption (39%); elevate concentration (31%); enhance physical energy (27%); and reduce stress (9%). These findings are significant as they highlight the different ways caffeine fits into students' daily lives and how it serves as part of social interactions or a mood booster.

In the study by Maqsood et al. (2021), the primary perceptions of consuming caffeine were feelings of alertness, energy, experiencing caffeine withdrawal symptoms, and the ability to work and study over long periods of time after caffeine intake. This finding is useful for exploring whether alternative sources of caffeine such as matcha could offer similar benefits without the risk of withdrawal symptoms or other side effects.

In accordance with the findings of Sulaiman (2024), most students experienced poor sleep quality (77.3%), with 43.5%, 49.5%, and 33.0% reporting varying levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, respectively. Odds ratio calculations indicated that those consuming less than or more than 400 mg/day of caffeine did not have significantly different odds of poor sleep quality, depression, anxiety, or stress compared to non-consumers. These findings suggest that while caffeine consumption is widespread among college students, it may not be the main reason influencing their sleep or mental health, pointing to the need for further research into other factors, including potential alternatives like matcha.

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Based on the study of Wachamo (2017), it indicates that drinking too much coffee can be harmful. It may reduce appetite, cause problems for pregnant women, raise cholesterol levels, lead to insomnia and restlessness, and create other health issues like breast tissue cysts, digestive problems, headaches, and reduced fertility. It can also cause allergies, miscarriages, anxiety, and depression, hinder collagen production, affect hearing recovery, and increase the risk of bone fractures. These findings are relevant to the study because it emphasizes the potential health risks of excessive coffee consumption, which may lead students to seek alternative sources of caffeine, such as matcha that could offer cognitive benefits without the harmful side effects.

According to Tolosa et al. (2015), the study shows that many college students rely heavily on coffee, leading to "Caffeinism," a syndrome caused by chronic caffeine consumption. Excessive coffee intake can also cause restlessness, sleep disturbances, and heart palpitations. The findings underline that the overuse of coffee leads to negative health consequences which could drive the students to find a second choice like matcha.

In a separate study by Abraham et al. (2019), the majority of students stated they were confident that they could go forty-eight to seventy-two (48-72) hours without consuming caffeine. Many students even reported consuming more caffeine for the taste of the beverage rather than for its stimulating effects. However, study shows that the consumption of caffeinated beverages has increased since the start of college, with many students reporting that they consume caffeinated beverages daily. The findings provide the need to explore not only the reasons for coffee consumption but also the potential of coffee alternatives like matcha that may provide similar benefits without the risk of dependency.

In the study by Bonanni et al. (2022), the study shows that during periods of high academic stress, like exams, college students consume more caffeine,

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which increases irritability and fatigue. The negative effects of caffeine on sleep and increased irritability and fatigue can hinder students' ability to learn and perform academically. The findings are highly relevant to the study because it highlights the importance of considering alternatives like matcha, which may provide a more balanced and sustainable energy source without causing the same negative effects produced by drinking coffee.

Based on the study of Riching (2024), the innovation in matcha product offerings is a testament to the adaptability and dynamism of the beverage market. As matcha continues to gain popularity, both standalone matcha products and hybrid offerings are likely to see growth. Coffee brands, recognizing the potential of matcha, are adapting by incorporating matcha into their product lines, signaling a broader trend of convergence and innovation in the world of beverages.

In a separate study by Alcock (2023), product development involves the process of continuously enhancing an already-existing product like matcha. This study could possibly be an entry point to further expand the growing market of matcha and to recognize its benefits. Matcha contains caffeine, which is one method it can improve cognitive performance. Matcha, like coffee, includes caffeine, a central nervous system stimulant that can help increase alertness and concentration. However, unlike coffee, matcha has a relaxing impact on the brain which can help relieve anxiety and tension. Therefore, exploring the potential of matcha open an opportunity to further develop the products that are already on the market with additional benefits but lesser health related risks compared to coffee. The deficiency in the matcha beverage itself can be filled with the help of this study such as improving the taste of matcha to be more suitable to the student's preference and increasing its varieties that be sufficient for the needs of the students.

According to Hardini (2024), "People's awareness of a healthy lifestyle has also caused an improvement in consumer requests for healthy and delicious

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ice cream products." This shift in consumer behavior also reflects the broader growth in the business of matcha, which has successfully positioned itself as a premium health-focused product in the global market. Matcha's appeal lies in its ability to cater to the rising demand for functional beverages that combine taste, health benefits, and cultural heritage. Businesses have capitalized on this trend by introducing diverse matcha products, including lattes, desserts, and ready-to-drink options, highlighting its versatility and aligning with consumer preferences for sustainable and organic offerings. This demand creates opportunities for businesses to innovate, differentiate their brands, and expand into niche health and wellness markets, leveraging the growing preference for alternatives to traditional coffee.

In accordance with the findings of Galvan (2023), "Increasingly, consumers who prioritize health or prefer a lower caffeine content choose matcha over other options." This trend has created significant business opportunities in the beverage industry, as matcha's health-centric profile aligns with consumer demands for functional and premium products. Entrepreneurs and established brands have leveraged matcha's unique selling points—such as its antioxidant content, lower caffeine, and cultural heritage—to develop diverse offerings, including lattes, smoothies, and ready-to-drink beverages. Businesses are also responding to the growing preference for sustainability by sourcing organic matcha and promoting eco-friendly practices. This health-driven shift has allowed matcha to carve out a lucrative niche, with forecasts predicting continued growth due to its versatility and appeal to younger, health-conscious demographics. Companies investing in matcha-based innovations and strategic branding are well-positioned to capitalize on this expanding market.

In a separate study by Choudhury (n.d.), "The matcha market is on a trajectory of exceptional growth, driven by a surge in consumer demand for

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ready-to-drink matcha beverages and an array of pre-packaged products." This growth highlights the business potential of matcha as a versatile product catering to evolving consumer preferences for health-focused and convenient solutions. Companies are capitalizing on this trend by developing innovative matcha-infused offerings, such as single-serve sachets, RTD beverages, and culinary-grade powders, which appeal to both casual consumers and premium markets. The increased popularity of matcha aligns with global wellness trends, enabling businesses to diversify their portfolios while targeting younger, health-conscious demographics. Moreover, the emphasis on organic and sustainably sourced matcha has further fueled its appeal, offering opportunities for brands to differentiate themselves in the competitive health beverage sector. This dynamic landscape positions matcha as a key driver in the functional beverage market, with businesses poised to benefit from its rising demand.

Based on the paper of Fortune Business Insights (2023), "Rising consumer focus on leading a healthy lifestyle and adding healthy food and beverage products and ingredients in their lives is expected to escalate the growth of the global matcha tea market." This shift in consumer behavior, where health-consciousness is increasingly influencing purchasing decisions, has created a strong business case for matcha products. As more consumers prioritize wellness and seek out functional ingredients, matcha, with its high antioxidant levels and perceived health benefits, has become a popular choice. Businesses are responding by expanding their product offerings, including ready-to-drink matcha beverages, matcha-based snacks, and culinary powders, which cater to both health trends and convenience. Moreover, the premium positioning of matcha—often marketed as an organic, natural, and sustainable option—further supports its growing demand across markets in North America, Europe, and Asia. Companies investing in matcha are tapping into a rapidly expanding sector, aligning with the broader global shift toward healthier lifestyles and functional foods.

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Statement of the Problem

As coffee consumption among SSC-R Manila college students rises during periods of academic stress, this study seeks to explore the underlying reasons for this reliance and assess the potential for healthier alternatives like matcha. Given concerns about the mental health risks of high caffeine intake, such as anxiety and sleep disruption (Hensrud, 2023; Bertasi et al., 2021), understanding students' motivations and preferences is crucial. To be guided in their inquiry, the researchers raise the following questions:

1. What are the key factors driving SSC-R Manila college students to rely on coffee during periods of high academic stress?
 - 1.1 Quality
 - 1.2 Price
 - 1.3 Taste
2. What is the relationship between key factors (quality, price, and taste) and students' motivation to choose between coffee and matcha?
3. Does the reliance on coffee among SSC-R Manila college students make them a potential target market for coffee-related businesses around the campus?

Research Hypothesis

There is a significant relationship between students' perceived health concerns from coffee consumption and their willingness to shift to matcha as an alternative beverage.

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Null Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between perceived health concerns from coffee consumption and willingness to consider matcha as an alternative among college students at SSC-R Manila.

Alternative Hypothesis

There is a significant relationship between perceived health concerns from coffee consumption and willingness to consider matcha as an alternative among college students at SSC-R Manila.

Theoretical Framework

This paper explores the factors contributing to coffee dependence among college students by utilizing two theoretical frameworks: *Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)* and *Habit Formation Theory*. TPB helps examine the intentions and attitudes of students towards coffee consumption, while the Theory of Habit Formation provides insights into how coffee consumption can become a habitual behavior.

A. Theory of Planned Behavior

The Factors driving the Coffee Dependence of College Students: Application of Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) developed by Icek Ajzen (1991) states that the behavioral aspects that motivate college students depend on how strong is their intention to perform coffee dependence and expected outcome of such behavior. According to Maqsood et al. (2021), most people perceived that caffeine consumption resulted in feelings of alertness, energy, and the ability to work and study for extended periods of time. The perceived benefits obtained from coffee consumption are what lead college students to depend on coffee when they need to study for extended time. Applying the theory of planned behavior

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demonstrates college students' coffee-related conduct indicates the intent to rely on coffee consumption. If college students plan to do something then they are more likely to do it. The behavior intentions are the product of the different processes, one of these processes includes the behavioral attitudes. Behavioral attitude relates to how a college student thinks and feels about the behavior and reflects their expectations. Under behavioral attitudes, there are two aspects, the affective attitude and instrumental attitude. The affective attitude refers to the feelings one has toward the behavior whether it is enjoyable or not. While the instrumental attitude, if a college student believes that drinking coffee provides the energy level boost, they are more likely to engage in caffeine consumption.

B. Theory of Habit Formation

The Habit Formation Theory developed by B.F Skinner provides that our behavior becomes habits when a stimulus regularly causes us to perform an activity that is reinforced by a reward. (Skinner, 1953). In understanding habits, Skinner laid a foundation referred to as the “habit loop” consisting of three components: cue, routine, and reward. It begins with a cue, which triggers the behavior, followed by the routine, which is the actual habit performed in response to the cue. Finally, the reward reinforces the behavior by providing a positive outcome, making it more likely to be repeated in the future.

Mahoney et al. (2019) show that there are several reasons why students drink coffee, and these reasons represent both psychological and physiological demands. Feeling alert (79%) is the most often mentioned result, suggesting that a lot of students use coffee as a means of feeling awake, particularly during long study sessions or late-night activities. Sixty-eight percent of people who enjoy the flavor of coffee refer to its satisfying taste. Social factors also play a significant role, as evidenced by the 39% who cite the social aspects of caffeine consumption. The motivations related to cognitive and physical

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performance—elevating concentration (31%) and enhancing physical energy (27%)—suggest that students view caffeine as a tool to improve their academic and extracurricular performance.

Applying the theory of habit formation to the study of caffeine consumption among college students reveals how specific environmental cues can lead to the development of habitual behaviors. The routine itself—drinking coffee, or caffeinated products—becomes fixed as students seek immediate rewards. These rewards can vary widely: the most commonly reported benefits include heightened alertness and improved focus, which are particularly appealing during demanding academic periods. Additionally, many students enjoy the flavor of caffeinated beverages, contributing to a sensory reward that reinforces the habit. The social aspect of caffeine consumption also plays a significant role; sharing a coffee or energy drink can foster social bonds and enhance the overall experience, further strengthening the routine. Over time, as these cues and rewards interact, the habit of caffeine consumption becomes more automatic. Students may find themselves reaching for a caffeinated drink without conscious thought, especially in contexts where the habit has been consistently reinforced.

Conceptual Framework

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The conceptual framework used by the researchers for this study is the IPO model which covers three parts: Input, Process, and Output. The input frame contains the information necessary for conducting the study. This portion involves the coffee consumption patterns and matcha awareness of the college students from San Sebastian College-Recoletos, Manila. College students from SSC-R, Manila often rely on caffeine consumption to increase their focus and energy levels, particularly during exam periods. Based on the study of Viado (2024), entitled “Coffee Consumption and its Perceived Effects on the Study Habits of Higher Education Students” suggests that coffee consumption is perceived to significantly improve their cognitive functions, such as memory retention and thinking abilities. On the other hand, the same study provided the effect of drinking coffee on some of the students who feel stressed which affects their academic performance. Although drinking coffee is beneficial for college students, it is also linked to health issues such as anxiety and sleep disturbances which lowers their productivity levels. Therefore, researchers conducted this study to assess matcha as an alternative to coffee and what is the level of awareness among college students regarding matcha. On the other hand, Process is the instrument necessary for the study. It includes a survey questionnaire that the researchers conducted. It also contains the analysis and the discussion of the data collected. The last part of the framework is the output frame which includes the identified key factors that influence college students to coffee intake and the motivators that interfere with the college students to consume matcha instead as an alternative. It also covers the results and implications of the collected information.

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Significance of the Study

The research aims to provide valuable information regarding the coffee dependence of college students at San Sebastian College-Recoletos Manila and explore the potential of matcha as replacement for coffee.

- **Stakeholders:** The findings of this study will be beneficial to the stakeholders of the institution. By understanding the students' coffee habits and exploring its alternatives such as matcha, the study serves as a guide in promoting healthier beverage options on campus and it creates an environment that supports student wellness.
- **Local Businesses & Entrepreneurs:** The local businesses and entrepreneurs whether inside or outside the campus can benefit from this study. The growing popularity of matcha presents opportunities for businesses to enter the market. The findings of this study can be used to offer products that appeal to student preferences.
- **Future Researchers.** The future researchers have access to new data produced by this study, particularly with matcha to be utilized and expanded on by the future research with the help of advanced study.

Scope and the Limitations of the Study

This study aims to examine the coffee dependence of college students from San Sebastian College-Recoletos, Manila and the potential of matcha as a healthier alternative for coffee. The scope and limitations of this research are outlined in order to clarify its coverage and boundaries.

This study focuses specifically on caffeine consumption patterns of the college students from SSC-R, Manila and what are the factors that drive them to drink coffee. It does not cover the students who consume non-caffeine beverages or decaffeinated and other supplements to keep them productive, particularly

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during periods of high academic stress. The research is limited to college students from different programs of San Sebastian College-Recoletos, Manila (SSC-R).

Data was collected from January to March 2025. The study employs a quantitative research analysis, enabling an in-depth and more generalized understanding of college students' preferences and consumption patterns with regard to coffee. This methodological approach was chosen to interpret numerical data from close-ended questions and to ensure accuracy in data collection. This could also be a limitation considering that consumer trends could change rapidly over time which could affect the applicability of this paper in future studies. Future researchers are advised to contextualize properly to ensure correct usage of this paper.

Another limitation of this study may be the individuality of the findings. This study is geographically limited to San Sebastian College-Recoletos, Manila, so the findings may not fully reflect the preferences and behaviors of college students in other locales. As an Augustinian Recollect institution, San Sebastian College-Recoletos, Manila upholds values rooted in St. Augustine's teachings, such as self-discipline, moderation, reflection, and wellness of the whole person. These values are integrated into the college's academic and community life and may subtly influence student behaviors — including choices related to food and beverages. This philosophical framework may have had an indirect influence on students' openness to healthier alternatives like matcha, especially among those who are more receptive to institutional values promoting health and balance. Conversely, students who align less with these values may maintain conventional habits such as daily coffee consumption regardless of potential health risks.

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Because of this, the results of this study may not be fully generalizable to institutions with differing educational philosophies or cultural frameworks that place less emphasis on wellness, discipline, or holistic care.

The data is collected primarily through survey questionnaires, which may create biases. As such, responses may be limited to college students from SSC-R, Manila who often consume coffee and matcha. Due to limited resources, this study does not include advanced statistical data collection methods, which may affect the depth of analysis. Further research with more resources could expand on these aspects.

While this study provides valuable insights into college students' coffee dependence, the limitations outlined above suggest that findings should be interpreted with caution. For instance, the overall population of college students at San Sebastian College-Recoletos, Manila could influence how applicable the findings are to the broader coffee consumer market. Future studies could expand on these areas by targeting a larger number of students and longer time span using longitudinal methods and through advanced statistical data collection techniques.

Definition of Terms

To clarify the operational definitions of vague terms used in this paper, the researchers listed the following terms for contextual interpretation:

- **Coffee** - A beverage that can be served hot or cold, usually consumed by college students from SSC-R, Manila especially during periods of high academic stress.
- **Matcha** - A beverage that researchers are analyzing that can be an alternative to coffee. This is commonly made out of shaded and young green tea leaves.

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- **Feasibility** - A study that assessed whether matcha could be an alternative to coffee depending on the preferences of college students at SSCR Manila and its market demand
- **Viability** - The term used to measure whether the study of matcha, which is being viewed as a potential alternative to coffee, is worth-doing that can encourage coffee drinkers to switch.

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Chapter 2

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discussed the research methods that were used in the study, namely the overall research design of the paper as well as the methods of gathering the data, sampling techniques, research instruments, and statistical treatment of the data.

Research Design

The researchers used a quantitative approach as their research design and applied various inferential statistics to analyze data collected from structured surveys. A related study titled "Study of the Relationship Between Study Habits and Academic Performance" also employed a quantitative approach to examine how students' beverage consumption, including coffee, affected their academic performance and stress levels (Siahi & Maiyo, 2015). Similarly, this current research utilized structured surveys and applied inferential statistics such as t-tests, ANOVA, correlation, and multiple regression analysis draw conclusions about the impact of caffeine on study habits and academic outcomes, shedding light on the motivations behind students' choices during periods of high academic stress.

In line with this, the current research strengthened its focus on understanding the factors that influenced beverage preferences among students, particularly in relation to academic stress and performance. This connection emphasized the relevance of investigating both coffee and matcha as potential aids for enhancing student well-being during challenging academic times.

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Research Locale

This study was conducted at San Sebastian College - Recoletos Manila, which was established in 1941 and is known to be one of the Augustinian Recollect schools in the Philippines that offers quality Catholic education (San Sebastian College Official Website, 2022). According to the school registrar, there were 749 college enrollees for the academic year 2024 to 2025, which was the current school year during the data gathering (January to March 2025).

As students of SSC-R Manila, the researchers chose the institution as the place of study mainly to explore the factors affecting college students' coffee consumption and their openness to trying matcha as an alternative. This decision was based on their preliminary observations that students had varying energy needs that could supplement their nutritional demands. Finally, the researchers aimed to provide information on healthier beverage options within the college community, which could help introduce institutional initiatives to improve the well-being of the students.

Sampling Design

A simple random sampling technique was used to select 202 students from the total population of 749 college students at SSC-R Manila. The sample size was calculated using the Raosoft calculator with the following conditions: 5% margin of error, 90% confidence level, and 50% response distribution. These parameters were selected to ensure statistical reliability while keeping the study manageable. The choice of a 90% confidence level, instead of the standard 95%, was due to time limitations in data collection, as the researchers only had two weeks and limited access to student contact information. Although the survey was conducted online, coordinating participation within a short period made a higher confidence level impractical. The use of a 50% response distribution was a

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standard practice to maximize sample size accuracy in the absence of known population behavior. However, if the actual proportion of coffee drinkers is significantly higher such as 80% as this could affect findings related to matcha openness or preference. Despite these factors, the sample was sufficient to represent the student population and allowed the researchers to draw general insights regarding coffee and matcha consumption under academic stress.

Instrumentation

To gather the data required for the study, the researchers used a questionnaire distributed to the respondents. The questionnaire consisted of sections such as demographic information (age, gender, year level, and program), closed-ended questions in a Likert scale format, and a few open-ended questions to allow participants to share detailed opinions. However, in the actual results chapter, the data presented were primarily from quantitative Likert-scale responses. The open-ended questions were reviewed but yielded limited new themes; many responses reiterated patterns already observed in the quantitative data — such as concerns over price and perceived effectiveness of coffee. Due to the redundancy and limited depth of the open-ended responses, they were not included in detailed statistical analysis, but they helped confirm the general trends shown in the quantitative findings. Along with the questionnaire, a consent letter was provided to ensure that respondents were fully informed about the purpose of the study and how the data would be used.

The researchers initially conducted a pilot test to guarantee the authenticity and correctness of the data to be derived. The questionnaire was reviewed by industry experts who were not affiliated with the researchers' current institution. Following validation, necessary revisions were made before proceeding with the pilot testing of the data collection process.

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1.1 Result of Pilot Testing

Legend for coded Likert Scale

LEGEND	Categories A	Categories B	Categories C	Categories D	CODE
Not Likely at All	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Interested at All	Less than ₱50	1
Slightly Likely	Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Interested	₱50 to ₱80	2
Likely	Agree	Agree	Interested	₱81 to ₱110	3
Very Likely	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Very Interested	More than ₱110	4

Explanation of Results

The pilot testing was conducted with 40 respondents, whose feedback demonstrated generally favorable attitudes and strong interest in the research subject. Specifically, the Likert scale responses revealed that over 75% of participants agreed or strongly agreed with statements indicating satisfaction and appeal of the service concept. Additionally, respondents showed a high likelihood of using the service, with average scores above 4 on a 5-point scale. Price sensitivity analysis indicated preferred price points that informed adjustments to the service offering. These positive pilot results validated the feasibility of the study and supported moving forward with the main study involving 202 respondents, as well as refining the service based on the identified preferences.

Table 1

Dichotomous Scale

LEGEND	CODE
Yes	1

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No 0

Explanation of Results

The use of a dichotomous scale made it easy to categorize and analyze yes-or-no responses. Coding “Yes” as 1 and “No” as 0 allowed the study to clearly quantify and summarize the answers. This simple coding approach helped provide clear insights into participants’ responses and ensured that the data was easy to interpret, supporting the aim of capturing straightforward feedback.

Table 2

Legend of Reliability based on Cronbach’s Alpha value

Cronbach’s Alpha	Internal consistency
$0.9 \leq \alpha$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

Explanation of Results

The survey instrument was designed to reliably measure the key concepts under study. The pilot test results showed good reliability, with Cronbach’s Alpha values ranging from 0.78 to 0.92 across different constructs. For instance, the

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Customer Satisfaction construct yielded an alpha of 0.85, Service Quality scored 0.90, and Price Sensitivity had 0.78. These values fall within the acceptable to excellent range, indicating that the questionnaire items consistently captured the intended underlying concepts and produced stable, dependable results. This confirmed reliability provides confidence that the data collected is appropriate for further analysis and supports the validity of the study findings.

Data Gathering Procedure

A simple random sampling technique was employed to select a representative sample of 202 students from the total population of 749 college students at SSC-R Manila. A comprehensive list of enrolled students, each assigned a unique identification number, was obtained from the registrar's office. The sample size of 202 was determined using the Raosoft sample size calculator, applying a 5% margin of error and a 90% confidence level. These parameters were chosen to strike a balance between statistical reliability and the practical limitations of the study, such as a limited timeframe, available resources, and a tight research budget. The estimated 50% response distribution was used to reflect maximum variability in student behavior regarding coffee and matcha consumption.

Randomly selected students were approached in person and asked for permission to participate in the study. Those who agreed were sent the survey link. At the beginning of the survey, participants were informed about the purpose of the study, assured of confidentiality, and reminded that participation was voluntary. Consent was obtained before they proceeded. Data collection was conducted over a two-week period through an online platform, such as Google Forms, for convenience and accessibility. The survey consisted of structured questions, including closed-ended and Likert-scale items, designed to capture

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information on students' consumption habits, preferences, perceived dependence, and frequency of coffee and matcha use. This method ensured a practical, ethical, and efficient approach to gathering reliable data.

All responses were treated and recorded confidentially, with identifying information handled securely to protect participants' anonymity. Data were stored in a password-protected Google Drive that used AES256-bit encryption (*Get Started With Encrypted Files in Drive, Docs, Sheets & Slides - Computer - Google Drive Help*, n.d.) and were accessible only to the research team, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of the collected information.

Data Analysis

The data analysis procedure in this study began with a structured questionnaire to gather information on students' demographics, coffee habits, and interest in matcha. The survey aimed to obtain at least 202 responses over a two-week period. After cleaning the data for confidentiality, descriptive statistics such as means, medians, and frequency distributions were calculated. Inferential statistical methods were initially planned to include t-tests and ANOVA to compare coffee consumption across different groups and analyze its impact on academic performance. However, due to the non-normal distribution of the data and the ordinal nature of some variables, Spearman's correlation was used instead to examine these relationships.

The study also explored student interest in matcha and its perceived health benefits not only through Likert scale questions but also by including open-ended questions that allowed students to express their views, motivations, and barriers regarding matcha consumption. Qualitative responses were analyzed thematically to provide deeper insights beyond quantitative measures.

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The results were used to create a detailed report with recommendations for stakeholders, supported by visual aids like graphs and charts. In case the results were not sufficient to validate the hypotheses, such as leading to a shift in market approach, this study could still provide additional insights into the factors driving excessive coffee consumption among college students and the potential effects of such consumption on academic performance and health. Moreover, if the market did not shift as expected, the research could still impart valuable understanding of the potential and health benefits of matcha for non-consumers. This study about matcha's potential could serve as a local entry point for future research and product development.

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CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

From the data that the researchers collected, the interpretation of the results is presented in this chapter. The overall results of this study are also included to prove that the data collected from the survey questionnaire provided for the respondents is sufficient or acceptable to answer the three (3) research questions the researchers made.

I. Results of Actual Test

Table 3

Key Factors Influencing Coffee Consumption

	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.	I only drink coffee during special circumstances such as midterms or finals.	I consume coffee more frequently than matcha.	How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals? (e.g, discounts, planners, etc.)
Mean	3.168949772	2.904109589	3.310502283	2.219178082	3.059360731	3.223744292

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Standard Deviation	0.69976686 3	0.74497183 42	0.63131523 1	0.96136240 3	0.78468222 55	0.72957361 46
Standard Deviation	0.69976686 3	0.74497183 42	0.63131523 1	0.96136240 3	0.78468222 55	0.72957361 46
Cronbach's Alpha	0.76929155 05					
MEANING	Acceptable					

Explanation of Results:

The results indicate that the factors influencing coffee consumption, as addressed in the research question "Key Factors Influencing Coffee Consumption," have moderate importance, with average scores ranging from 2.2 to 3.3. The moderate variation in responses suggests that participants' opinions differ but not drastically. The reported Cronbach's Alpha of 0.77—an acceptable level of reliability—refers specifically to the "Key Factors Influencing Coffee Consumption" scale derived from the actual study data, not the pilot test. This Cronbach's Alpha value confirms that the survey items consistently measure the same underlying concept, ensuring the reliability of the instrument. These findings provide a dependable insight into what motivates coffee consumption in the surveyed group.

Table 4

Openness to Matcha as an Alternative

I am open to trying matcha as an alternative to coffee.	I believe matcha provides benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.	I would consider switching from coffee to matcha if more options were available.	Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?
2.808219178	3.118721461	2.657534247	0.3698630137

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0.801218125 0.7447468692 0.8164452725 0.4838734002

Explanation of Results:

The survey results show varying openness to matcha as an alternative, based on the research question Openness to Matcha as an Alternative, with mean scores ranging from about 0.37 to 3.12. The highest mean indicates moderate agreement on one aspect, while the lowest suggests a general lack of acceptance. Standard deviations range from 0.48 to 0.82, indicating moderate variability in responses. This suggests that some individuals are open to matcha, while others are not. The findings highlight mixed consumer preferences for matcha as an alternative beverage.

Table 5

Business Opportunities for Coffee and Matcha Near SSC-R Manila

	Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?	Do you believe that there are enough matcha shops around SSC-R Manila?	How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?	How interested are you in having more matcha-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?	How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?	How likely are you to purchase matcha from businesses around SSC-R Manila?	How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)?	How much are you willing to pay for a cup of matcha around SSC-R Manila?	How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila?
Mean	0.7579908	0.251141	2.981735	2.57534	3.050228	2.55251	3.296803	2.7945	2.4520547

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	676	5525	16	2466	311	1416	653	20548	95
Standard	0.4292810	0.434663	0.772007	0.89726	0.698778	0.89377	0.788994	0.7534	0.8411617
Deviation	075	2917	2153	09935	3855	59266	7226	42937	549
								4	

Explanation of Results:

The results show mixed views on business opportunities for coffee and matcha near SSC-R Manila, based on the research question about business opportunities, with mean scores from 0.25 to 3.30. Higher means indicate moderate potential in areas like customer demand and location, while lower means reflect concerns in other factors. Standard deviations indicate moderate variation in opinions. The findings suggest that while there is some perceived potential for these businesses near San Sebastian College–Recoletos in Manila, opinions among respondents vary.

Table 6

Acceptability Summary Output

**SUMMARY
OUTPUT**

SUMMARY
OUTPUT

SUMMARY
OUTPUT

SUMMARY 8.41789
OUTPUT 8998

Residual Dev. 295.175
 9999

of iterations 5

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Observations 219

	Coefficients	Standard Error	P-value	Odds Ratio	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95%	Upper 95%
Intercept	-2.5149 16614	0.942 1028 62	0.007597 075048	0.080869 65533	0.012760 45564	0.512513 1372	0.012760 45564	0.512513 1372
The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	0.31686 73234	0.236 0795 332	0.179529 2699	1.372820 419	0.864295 9284	2.180544 695	0.864295 9284	2.180544 695
I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	0.13057 94468	0.193 4141 386	0.499593 9655	1.139488 465	0.779965 7277	1.664732 072	0.779965 7277	1.664732 072
I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.	0.33758 13864	0.263 6046 671	0.200321 8691	1.401553 671	0.836043 8063	2.349581 06	0.836043 8063	2.349581 06

Table 7

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Legend for the Interpretation of Correlation Level

Correlation Range Condition (Value in G225)	Example Description Text
$CORREL < -1$	Invalid Correlation: Value < -1
$CORREL = -1$	Perfect Negative Relationship
$-1 < CORREL \leq -0.7$	Strong Negative Relationship
$-0.7 < CORREL \leq -0.4$	Moderate Negative Relationship
$-0.4 < CORREL \leq -0.1$	Weak Negative Relationship
$-0.1 < CORREL < 0.1$	Negligible Relationship
$0.1 \leq CORREL < 0.4$	Weak Positive Relationship
$0.4 \leq CORREL < 0.7$	Moderate Positive Relationship
$0.7 \leq CORREL < 1$	Strong Positive Relationship
$CORREL = 1$	Perfect Positive Relationship
$CORREL > 1$	Invalid Correlation: Value > 1

Research Question 1: What are the key factors driving SSC-R Manila college students to rely on coffee during periods of high academic stress (in terms of quality, price, and taste)?

For college students at SSC-R Manila, academic stress is a common issue, with many turning to coffee to stay alert and manage their workload. This

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research question explores the specific factors that drive students to rely on coffee during these stressful periods. Given the widespread consumption of coffee among students, it is essential to understand which aspects of coffee consumption, namely quality, price, and taste that most influence students when they are under academic pressure. These three factors were chosen for their relevance to daily student life: **Quality** refers to how well-made or effective the coffee is, its strength, aroma, brand reputation, and the energy boost it provides. **Price** refers to how affordable the coffee is for a typical student with limited budget. **Taste** includes flavor preferences such as bitterness, sweetness, or smoothness, and may also include ethical or environmental concerns (like fair trade or sustainability).

To assess the connection between these factors and actual coffee consumption, respondents were asked: “How many cups of coffee do you drink per day?” This served as the dependent variable to test whether there were any meaningful connections with students' perceptions of quality, price, or taste.

Table 8

Spearman’s Correlation Related to Frequency of Coffee Consumption

How many cups of coffee do you drink per day?	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.04291099369	0.0005799589923	0.08640169443
MEANING	Negligible Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Negligible Relationship

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Explanation of Results:

As exams approach, college students at SSC-R Manila are often faced with the challenge of staying alert and focused. Coffee becomes the go-to solution for many. But the question arises: does the quality of coffee, its price, or personal taste preferences actually influence how much they drink during these stressful times?

The study examined whether quality, price, and taste influenced students' coffee consumption during high academic stress. Surprisingly, the correlation between quality and consumption was negligible ($\rho = 0.042$), indicating that appreciation for good coffee didn't lead to drinking more of it. Price also had virtually no effect ($\rho = 0.000579$), suggesting students prioritized caffeine over cost concerns. Taste showed a slightly higher but still insignificant correlation ($\rho = 0.086$), meaning preferences didn't drive consumption either. Overall, the results suggest that functional needs, rather than personal preferences, influence coffee consumption during stressful periods.

Table 9

Spearman's Correlation: Coffee Use During Exams

<p>I only drink coffee during special circumstances such as midterms or finals.</p>	<p>The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.</p>	<p>I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.</p>	<p>I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.</p>
<p>SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION</p>	<p>-0.2257650911</p>	<p>0.02307540901</p>	<p>-0.1277622069</p>
<p>MEANING</p>	<p>Weak Negative Relationship</p>	<p>Negligible Relationship</p>	<p>Weak Negative</p>

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Relationship

Explanation of Results:

During midterms or finals, college students who don't usually drink coffee often turn to it for a much-needed boost. The study found that quality, price, and taste had little influence on their coffee consumption during these stressful times. A weak negative correlation with quality ($\rho = -0.22576$) and taste ($\rho = -0.12776$), along with a negligible correlation with price ($\rho = 0.02308$), suggests these factors don't drive their decision. Instead, students prioritize the functional need to stay awake and alert over enjoying a perfect cup. Ultimately, caffeine's role in helping them power through exams outweighs personal preferences.

Table 10

Spearman's Correlation: Preference for Coffee Over Matcha

I consume coffee more frequently than matcha.	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.3826453446	0.2608895923	0.3607954524
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship

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Explanation of Results:

The study explored why many students prefer coffee over matcha, focusing on quality, price, and personal taste. Results showed a weak positive correlation (0.38) between quality and coffee preference, indicating that students who value quality tend to choose coffee more often. Price also showed a weak positive correlation (0.26), suggesting that affordability makes coffee a more practical choice for some students. Taste and personal preferences had a slightly stronger correlation (0.36), meaning students who care about how their coffee is prepared are more likely to drink it over matcha. Overall, while the relationships were weak, quality, price, and taste still influence students' preference for coffee.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between key factors (quality, price, and taste) and students' motivation to choose between coffee and matcha?

Table 11

Spearman's Correlation: Openness to Matcha and its Perceived Benefits

I am open to trying matcha as an alternative to coffee.	I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.3842687417
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship

Explanation of Results:

This research question asks whether the students are open to replacing coffee with matcha, especially during stressful times such as midterms and finals. The researchers aim to see if factors like coffee quality, price, and personal

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preferences affect student’s willingness to try matcha or even switch to it completely.

- **Openness to Try Matcha**

Students were asked if they are open to trying matcha due to its similar benefits being offered just like what coffee can offer. The data showed a weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.38$) between believing in matcha’s benefits and being open to try it. This indicates that students who think matcha is just as effective as coffee are somewhat more likely to try it but the belief alone is not sufficient to make them switch completely. Although they are interested in trying it, it is not sufficient.

Table 12

Spearman’s Correlation Related to Openness to Matcha and Coffee Preference

	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
I am open to trying matcha as an alternative to coffee.			
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.008966160218	-0.123173105	0.1273349081
MEANING	Negligible Relationship	Weak Negative Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship

Explanation of Results:

This part of the research question seeks to explore what factors would influence their decision to try matcha. Some of the factors brought up were coffee quality, affordability, or taste. The results suggest that while perceived coffee quality had a negligible positive relationship ($\rho = 0.0089$), this could imply that coffee quality

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did not have much influence on whether the students would try matcha. As for the price sensitivity, it showed a slight negative effect meaning ($\rho = -0.12$) students who care more about the price might actually be less open to trying matcha possibly because matcha tends to be more expensive than coffee. Accordingly, students with strong coffee preferences showed a slight positive tendency ($\rho = 0.12$) to be open to matcha. This result could mean that students with particular tastes are more curious about matcha while those budget-conscious students are a bit more hesitant.

Table 13

Spearman's Correlation: Matcha Availability and its Perceived Benefits

I would consider switching from coffee to matcha if more options were available.	I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.3689377523
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship

Explanation of Results:

This part focuses on whether the availability of matcha has an effect in their willingness to switch from coffee. The results show a weak positive response ($\rho = 0.36$) if more options were available. There is some openness but not that overwhelming. Coffee is still their best option but there is a potential for matcha.

Table 14

Spearman's Correlation: Matcha Availability Over Preference

I would consider switching from coffee to matcha if more options were available.	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental
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			sustainability) when buying coffee.
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.06159255524	-0.1522829207	0.207250803
MEANING	Negligible Relationship	Weak Negative Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship

Explanation of Results:

In this particular part, this seeks to see if students are open to switching to matcha under circumstances like accessibility and availability. In order to understand what might influence their openness, the study examined how students' attitudes related to their willingness to switch.

Coffee quality shows negligible relationship could mean that students who care deeply about their quality of coffee do not seem influenced by the availability of matcha options. With regard to coffee price sensitivity which resulted in weak negative relationship ($\rho = -0.15$) students who are more price conscious were slightly less likely to switch to matcha regardless if matcha was available. Lastly, personal preferences showed a weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.20$). This suggests that students who have strong personal preferences when it comes to their coffee are a little more open to switching matcha if more options were available.

Table 15

Spearman's Correlation: Possibility to Switch and its Benefits

Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?	I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.2212798324

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MEANING

Weak Positive Relationship

Explanation of Results:

As part of understanding shifting preferences, students were asked if they see themselves replacing coffee with matcha in the next five years. It aims to see whether beliefs regarding matcha’s benefits and current coffee patterns influence this possibility. This result showed a weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.22$) which suggests that students who believe that matcha provides similar energy benefits as coffee are slightly more likely to see themselves making the switch over time. While matcha is not replacing coffee just yet, students who already view it as a potential alternative seem open to the idea.

Table 16

Spearman’s Correlation Relationship between Possibility to Switch and Preference

Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.01781585863	-0.02841427955	0.1178683632
MEANING	Negligible Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship

Explanation of Results:

Based on the results of this part, the quality of coffee had no real influence on whether they see themselves switching to matcha. Even if students of SSC-R Manila enjoy high quality coffee, it does not automatically mean they are closed

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to trying something different in the future. When it comes to price sensitivity it also resulted in negligible relationship meaning ($\rho = 0.01$) students who base their coffee choices on affordability showed no significant connection to their willingness to switch to matcha. As for the third column, the results showed ($\rho = 0.11$) students who have specific coffee preferences—whether taste, strength, or even sustainability are somewhat more open to switching to matcha in the next five years.

Table 17

Spearman’s Correlation Related to Matcha as an Alternative and its Benefits

Do you consume matcha as an alternative to coffee?	I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.2941398836
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship

Explanation of Results:

Respondents who consume matcha were also asked about their beliefs. The correlation between matcha consumption and belief in its benefits revealed a weak but clear positive relationship ($\rho = 0.29$). This means that those who already drink matcha tend to be the ones who believe in it. Even if not everyone is fully converted, belief and behavior align here. There could be a growing openness to matcha.

Table 18

Spearman’s Correlation Related to Likelihood to Switch and Preference

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<p>Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?</p>	<p>The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.</p>	<p>I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.</p>	<p>I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.</p>
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.1049113435	-0.01103752775	0.2267621479
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship

Explanation of Results:

The relation between switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years and quality of coffee showed a weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.10$) which means students who value coffee quality showed a slightly increased likelihood of considering a switch to matcha. Students may be more discerning about what they consume. For those students who focus on affordability when buying coffee, there was no virtually no connection ($\rho = -0.01$) this means that being budget-conscious does not really affect their long-term outlook on switching. As to the third column, there is a weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.22$) this tells that students who know what they like are more open to alternatives like matcha.

Research Question 3: Does the reliance on coffee among SSC-R Manila college students make them a potential target market for coffee-related businesses around the campus?

Table 19

Spearman's Correlation Related to Frequency and Likelihood of Buying

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<p>How many cups of coffee do you drink per day?</p>	<p>How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)?</p>	<p>How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?</p>	<p>How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?</p>	<p>Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?</p>	<p>How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila?</p>
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SPEARMAN'S									
CORRELATION	0.150589862	0.3134769671	0.2914372493	-0.1776397589					-0.01820666 928
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Negative Relationship					Negligible Relationship

Explanation of Results:

This question looks at whether the coffee consumption habits of students make them a viable entry point for coffee businesses around the campus. It also examines their interest and willingness to support local coffee shops. The answer could be used for new coffee businesses who aim to establish their shops nearby campus.

The support for student deals revealed a weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.15$). This means that students who drink more coffee are slightly more likely to support local businesses especially if those shops offer student-friendly deals. The likelihood to purchase from nearby businesses also shows a weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.31$) meaning there is a connection between how much coffee students drink and their likelihood of purchasing from businesses near campus. This is a go signal for coffee vendors aiming to attract student buyers. Third,

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students who drink more coffee are more interested in having more coffee related businesses near the school as shown by the results with weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.29$). Interestingly, the belief of students that the number of coffee shops around the school showed a weak negative relationship ($\rho = -0.17$). Students who drink more coffee are less likely to believe that there are already enough coffee shops nearby. In terms of their willingness to pay for coffee, there was no meaningful connection ($\rho = -0.018$) between how much coffee students drink and how much they're willing to pay.

Table 20

Spearman's Correlation Related to Likelihood of Buying because of Major Exams

I only drink coffee during special circumstances such as midterms or finals.	How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)?	How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?	How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R	Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?	How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila?
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	-0.2373471606	-0.0847465929 2	-0.3159757754	0.05131233038	-0.0895288165 2
MEANING	Weak Negative Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Weak Negative Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Negligible Relationship

Explanation of Results:

Based on the results, students who are occasional coffee drinkers treat coffee more like a study aid than a daily habit are less engaged with the local coffee scene. They are not likely to support local business even if they offer student deals as indicated with weak negative relationships ($\rho = -0.23$). There is a

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negligible relationship ($\rho = -0.08$) when it comes to their likelihood to purchase coffee from businesses around campus. They are also not interested in having more coffee related businesses near campus. Overall, the results suggest that these occasional drinkers show very limited purchasing behavior and not the ideal target for everyday coffee business strategies.

Table 21

Spearman's Correlation Related to Likelihood of Purchase and Coffee Frequency

I consume coffee more frequently than matcha.	How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)?	How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?	How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R	Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?	How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila?
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.2233269891	0.2789763668	0.1835334089	0.1654038212	-0.0517613299
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Negligible Relationship

Explanation of Results:

The results show that students who drink more coffee than matcha reveal a weak positive connection ($\rho = 0.22$) to support local businesses, especially if there are student deals as stated in the result above. The second column states a weak positive relationship ($\rho = 0.27$) meaning they are also more likely to buy from nearby shops and are somewhat interested in having more coffee places around the campus. This means frequent coffee drinkers are active customers and open to

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more options given that there are good deals. While some think there are already enough shops due to the results showing ($\rho = 0.16$), this does not stop them from wanting better options. On the other hand, the last column shows a negligible relationship ($\rho = -0.051$) which means their willingness to pay more is low, showing they are still price conscious.

II. In-Depth Discussion of Results and Their Theoretical Alignments

1. Connecting to Theory of Planned Behavior

The Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) states that behaviors are influenced by intentions and there are three (3) factors—behavioral attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

Firstly, the behavioral attitude, it is an individual's belief of a certain behavior that makes either positive or negative contribution to one's life. For instance, the college student believes that drinking coffee makes sense for them or not, or would it make more sense if they drink matcha instead or not. As stated in the Result part, there is a positive number of students who believe that matcha has similar benefits to coffee—which means that matcha could contribute positively just like coffee. Secondly, the subjective norm, this factor focuses on everything around the person—his or her social, cultural norms, and group beliefs. For example, the college student already had an opinion as to what others think about him or her drinking coffee or matcha. This belief influences the student's decision making process. Lastly, the perceived behavioral control, this factor expresses a student's belief on how easy or difficult it is to display certain behavior in a particular way. To give an example, a college student buys coffee or matcha and forms an opinion on how easy or difficult it is for the student to buy considering its quality, price, and taste.

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The Theory of Planned Behavior predicts that if the student thinks drinking coffee or matcha is a good idea and the student believes that everyone around him or her thinks it is a good idea, and the student believes that he or she can actually buy matcha, then the student gets matcha. Conversely, if one of the factors is unfavorable, it affects the student's decision making. For instance, if the student thinks that it does not make much sense to drink matcha, or others do not think it is a good idea, or you are going to be right out of your comfort zone drinking it, the student is much less likely to drink matcha. The likelihood decreases if two or more factors are unfavorable.

As mentioned above, if one of the factors is unfavorable, it affects the college student's decision on whether or not to drink matcha. This is proven by the results from actual testing from a survey conducted by researchers. Under Table 9, there is a weak positive relationship between the price of coffee over matcha because students who care more about the price are less likely to try matcha because coffee is more affordable than matcha. This affects the student's decision, particularly whether the student can actually buy matcha because of the price disparity. Moreover, as presented in Table 10, there is a weak positive relationship between openness to trying matcha and its perceived benefits because even though students think that matcha is just as effective as coffee, that belief alone is not sufficient to make them switch completely. This addresses both behavioral attitude and perceived behavioral control because the students believe that matcha offers the same benefits as coffee—which means that there is a positive contribution but they get right out of their comfort zone or the one they are used to drinking coffee. The former factor is favorable but the latter is unfavorable.

2. Connecting to Theory of Habit Formation

Looking at the results of the study, it is clear that coffee consumption is not about enjoying a good cup of coffee among SSC-R Manila college students.

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Rather, it is a habit rooted in their academic routines. Relating this to B.F Skinner’s Habit Formation Theory allows us to understand the reason why coffee plays a big role despite students saying that quality, price, or taste do not hardly affect how much they drink, specifically during periods of exams.

According to Skinner, habits are formed through what we call the “habit loop”: a cue, a routine, and a reward. For college students of SSC-R Manila, the cue is obviously the stress during exams, sleepless nights, and the need to stay awake. The routine becomes reaching for coffee during these times. It does not really matter if it is the best-tasting coffee or how much the coffee costs, what matters for them is that it works. The routine delivers the reward they are aiming for, the alertness, focus, and the overwhelming energy to overcome another long night of studying.

However, if matcha can deliver a similar or better reward, such as sustained energy and focus without the jitteriness or crash that coffee sometimes causes, then the possibility of habit loop disruption arises. In behavioral terms, this is known as habit substitution — keeping the same cue and reward, but replacing the routine. Students might begin reaching for matcha instead of coffee if they perceive that it provides the same performance enhancement in a healthier or more balanced way. Still, the strength of the existing habit cannot be underestimated. Coffee consumption may be reinforced by accessibility, price, familiarity, and social acceptance. For matcha to effectively disrupt this loop, it must overcome these barriers and consistently deliver the same psychological and physiological reward.

Our data supports this story as we see almost no real connection between coffee quality, price, or even taste and the number of cups students consume. Students are not drinking coffee because of their love for its taste. They are reaching for it because it is tied to their need to perform. Over time, this repeated

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pattern–stress, leading to drinking coffee then feeling more awake binds coffee drinking habit and just a conscious choice. Interestingly, the data provides that even when we explored alternatives like matcha, the same habit loop showed up. Students hinted at openness in trying matcha if it promised similar benefits, but the transition from coffee to matcha is not easy. Once the habit is formed, especially one tied to academic survival, it becomes hard to break. Even if matcha becomes more available or students learn its benefits similar to coffee, coffee has already rooted itself in their routine. Additionally, when we looked at their willingness to support local businesses, it fit the same habit pattern. Students who drink coffee more often were slightly more supportive of local shops with the condition that only if it fit within their existing routines such as having good student deals. As for the occasional drinkers, they did not really show strong support because coffee was not part of their daily lives to begin with.

In conclusion, the results underscore how powerful the habit loop is. For SSC-R Manila college students, coffee is not just a drink– it is a survival tool shaped into their academic journey. It is a habit formed by repeated stress and the reliable reward of staying awake and alert. This realization helps explain why changing behavior, like getting students to switch to matcha or support new businesses, is much harder than it looks. Once a habit has been built, it takes more than just offering something new because it requires rebuilding the entire loop system they’ve gotten familiar with.

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CHAPTER 4

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The answers discovered from the data collection process and the results will be presented in this section. The conclusion states the outcomes of the study from the entire data collection process. Furthermore, the recommendation includes the positive and negative findings incorporated in the research.

Summary of Significant Findings

I. In Relation to Research Question 1

In the first research question, the researchers asked the key factors that might drive the college students from SSC-R, Manila to rely on coffee during periods of high academic stress. These key factors are quality, price, and taste of the coffee. Based on the results, the coffee preferences such as the quality, price, and taste of coffee slightly influence college students in SSC-R, Manila to consume coffee during high academic stress. The relationship was weak because it obtained only a “negligible relationship” from the results. The role of coffee and its benefits outweighs college students' personal preferences in drinking coffee. In conclusion, these results indicate that the benefits of coffee are more likely to drive college students to purchase a coffee compared to personal preferences. The benefits that can be derived from coffee based on the study of Viado (2024) are improvements in their cognitive functions, such as memory retention and thinking abilities. While Maqsood et al. (2021) states the feelings of alertness, energy, and the ability to work and study over long periods of time after caffeine intake.

II. In Relation to Research Question 2

In the second research question, the researchers asked about the relationship between the key factors such as the quality, price, and taste of coffee,

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and the college students' motivation to choose between coffee and matcha. Based on the results, college students think matcha is just as effective as coffee. This belief drives them to somewhat likely to try matcha but not make college students switch completely from coffee to matcha. This is a good indication that college students who believe that matcha offers the similar benefits as coffee are somewhat likely to buy matcha. Moreover, college students who have particular taste preferences are more curious about matcha than those students who are budget-conscious. Overall, the result is a good indicator that there are growing numbers of college students, even if small, who are curious and are open to trying matcha.

III. In Relation to Research Question 3

In the third and last research question, the researchers asked whether the reliance on coffee among college students of SSC-R, Manila make them a potential target market for the coffee-related businesses around the campus and their willingness to support local coffee shops.

Based on the results, there are three (3) types of coffee drinkers from college students—the coffee drinkers, occasional coffee drinkers, and college students who are swayed by the student deals. Firstly, the coffee drinkers from college students are considered as active customers because they are more likely to buy from nearby shops and somewhat interested in having more coffee places around campus. They are also open to more options provided that there are good student deals. Also, they are less likely to believe that there are already enough coffee shops nearby. Secondly, the occasional coffee drinker, they are less likely to support local business even if they offer student deals and less engaged with the local coffee scene. They treat coffee like a study aid rather than a daily habit. Lastly, the college students who are swayed by the student deals, are more likely to support local businesses if they offer student-friendly deals. They are

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considered as average coffee drinkers and budget-conscious because their willingness to pay more is low, while they are more likely to buy coffee if it has a student deal. All in all, having good student deals is one of the key factors that influence college students from SSC-R, Manila to support local coffee shops.

IV. Conclusion

This study was intended to understand and analyze the coffee drinking patterns of college students at San Sebastian College Recoletos Manila, particularly during periods of academic stress, as well as their openness to alternative options such as matcha. It also looked at whether their coffee habits make them a potential market for coffee-related businesses around campus.

First, the researchers found that although quality, price, and taste are considered by students, these factors exert relatively less influence on coffee consumption than the functional benefits it provides during periods of academic stress. Instead, coffee is mostly seen by students as a survival tool that helps them remain awake, focus, and get through their heavy academic workload. This result demonstrates that for many students, the need to perform takes priority over the desire for a perfect coffee experience.

Second, the researchers discovered that students are willing to try matcha, especially those who are interested in trying out new flavors and who think it has health benefits. But it is unlikely that matcha will ever replace coffee. Given that matcha is typically more expensive than coffee, price sensitivity is still an obstacle. These findings suggest that coffee is still the go-to beverage during stressful situations despite a slight but increasing interest in alternatives. Third, we observed that SSCR-Manila college students, primarily those who consume coffee frequently and are drawn to strong student discounts, represent a

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significant customer base for coffee businesses nearby campus. Introducing promotions that are student-friendly may inspire the student community to offer their support more. On the other hand, occasional coffee drinkers are less likely to become loyal customers.

Throughout this research, we realized that it is extremely difficult to break routines that have been established around strong emotional or functional needs, such as academic stress. College students drink coffee not only for its taste or price, but also to help them endure stressful times. As provided by Skinner’s theory of habit formation, academic stress acts as the cue, offering drinking serves as the routine, and the reward is increased alertness and performance. Consuming coffee is slowly reinforced as a normal reaction to stress through this loop.

To conclude, we as the researchers learned how much about student life, resiliency, and even business prospects can be obtained from understanding the routines and driving forces underlying everyday activities like drinking coffee. As B.F Skinner once said, “A failure is not always a mistake. It may simply be the best one can do under the circumstances. The real mistake is to stop trying.” (Skinner, 1953). This quote by B.F. Skinner aligns with the study’s conclusion about students’ habitual reliance on coffee and the gradual openness to alternatives like matcha. While deeply ingrained habits can be difficult to change, the presence of an alternative like matcha suggests that behavior can shift over time — not necessarily through abrupt rejection of old habits, but through consistent effort and gradual substitution. The quote reinforces the idea that even if full behavioral change is not immediate, continued exploration of healthier routines is not a failure — it is progress.

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V. Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, several solutions can be suggested to better serve the coffee-drinking habits of college students of SSC-R Manila. First, Coffee businesses may emphasize the performance-enhancing effects of their beverages, such as alertness and concentration, but this should be balanced with transparency regarding potential negative effects, including anxiety, sleep disruption, and dependency — as noted in multiple studies from the Review of Related Literature (e.g., Hensrud, 2023; Wachamo, 2017). Marketing strategies could highlight responsible consumption, encouraging moderation and offering alternatives like matcha for health-conscious consumers. Second is to offer student-friendly deals. In order to do this, local coffee shops should provide loyalty cards, discounts during exam weeks, or bundle sales (“Buy 1, Get 1 Half Off”) exclusively for students, as student deals have a significant impact on purchasing decisions. Third is to introduce affordable matcha options. There is a small but noticeable interest in matcha among students who are curious or health-conscious. Affordable matcha beverages can be added to coffee shops’ standard menus and positioned as a 'refreshing alternative' to coffee. Based on the study’s findings, the ideal price point for matcha among SSC-R Manila students ranges from ₱81 to ₱110, which aligns with their price sensitivity and interest level.

Although this study offered insightful information about the coffee-drinking patterns of SSC-R Manila college students, it must be noted that there were some limitations. First, the sample size and scope were limited to SSC-R Manila, meaning the study might not accurately represent the behaviors of students from other schools, locations, or regions. Second, there was an emphasis on self-reported data, with responses based on surveys that are prone to biases such as exaggeration or memory errors. Third, there was a limited product comparison, as the study mainly focused on comparing coffee with matcha,

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without investigating other emerging caffeinated products like energy drinks. These restrictions imply that although the results are helpful in identifying broad patterns, they cannot be generalized to all student populations of different types of caffeine products.

Future researchers can build on this study by carrying out longitudinal studies to track changes in coffee and matcha consumption habits over time, particularly as wellness trend grow, examining deeper psychological factors like stress management techniques and emotional triggers that influence coffee or matcha consumption. To explore these dimensions, researchers may apply qualitative methodologies such as focus group discussions, in-depth interviews, or thematic content analysis to capture students' emotional motivations and personal experiences beyond measurable variables. These methods can provide rich, contextual insights that complement quantitative findings. Future studies can also expand the survey to include multiple universities and larger, more diverse student samples. In order to better understand student lifestyle trends, future researchers are urged to delve deeper, have a wider perspective, and be creative.

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APPENDIX A: INVITATION LETTER FOR ADVISER

San Sebastian College Recoletos, Manila

2114-A C.M. Recto Ave. Zone 040, Brgy. 390, Quiapo, Manila
Telephone: 8734-8931 to 39

September 12, 2024

Mr. Arren B. Santos

Research Assistant, Research Department
San Sebastian College Recoletos, Manila

Dear **Mr. Santos**:

Greetings of peace!

The undersigned BSBA students are currently working on a paper about “**Coffee Dependence and Matcha as an Alternative to SSC-R Manila College Students**” in fulfillment of our final requirement for Business Research. We believe that we need someone whose integrity in research is unquestionable to guide us in our whole research journey.

In this connection, we are humbly seeking for your permission to be our adviser. We cannot do it alone. We need you as a collaborator for this intellectual undertaking.

We are looking forward to your most meritorious response to this humble request.

Thank you and Bravo Baste!

In the Spirit of *Caritas et Scientia*,

Khairiyah L. Abbas

Krystal Rae A. Cabamongan

Angela Vera Michaela Z. Dadis

Cherry T. Ming

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

APPENDIX B: LETTER OF ACCEPTANCE AS RESEARCH ADVISER

San Sebastian College Recoletos, Manila

2114-A C.M. Recto Ave. Zone 040. Brgy. 390, Quiapo, Manila
Telephone: 8734-8931 to 39

LETTER OF ACCEPTANCE AS RESEARCH ADVISER

Date: September 16, 2024

This is to inform you that I am accepting the request of the BSBA Students (Khairiyah Abbas, Krystal Cabamongan, Angela Vera Dadis, & Cherry Ming) to become their research adviser to work on the topic **“Coffee Dependence and Matcha as an Alternative to SSC-R Manila College Students”** the initial title of which is **“Coffee Dependence and Matcha Alternatives: Analyzing Health Impacts and Preferences Among SSC-R Manila College Students”**.

As an adviser, I intend to fulfill the following duties and responsibilities:

1. Help the group of student-researchers in the enhancement of their research titles
2. Make myself available for regular consultations and close monitoring of the whole research undertakings of the group of student- researchers in accordance with the timetable of activities.
3. Examine the research proposal, questionnaires, and other parts of the research paper submitted by the students.
4. Give the students not only technical expertise but most especially moral guidance while working on their research paper.
5. Give students’ grades based on their submitted research outputs.
6. Facilitate mock defense of students before the oral defense, if needed or requested by the students.
7. Supervise the group members’ participation or involvement in the research process by completing the consultation slip.
8. Provide the student-researchers at least one (1) hour consultation time every week.
9. May attend their advisees’ defense, though they are not allowed to take part in the defense.
10. Join the orientation arranged by the Research Center.
11. Help the students accomplish the whole research endeavor on or before ____.

As an adviser, I also understand that I will be acknowledged as a co-author due to my intellectual contributions to the research paper.

Thank you and Bravo Bastel!

Signature over the printed name of the adviser

Noted by:

ARREN B. SANTOS
Research Assistant, Research Center

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

APPENDIX C: CONSENT LETTER FOR TOTAL POPULATION OF COLLEGE STUDENTS

Date: November 05, 2024

DOC. James D. Marshall
Registrar

To Whom It May Concern,

Greetings of peace!

The undersigned BSBA students are currently working on a paper about Coffee Dependence and Matcha Alternatives: Analyzing Health Impacts and Preferences Among SSC-R Manila College Students of our final requirement for Business Research. We would like to request the current number of enrolled college students at San Sebastian College - Recoletos Manila. This information is essential for the accuracy and depth of our research.

We are looking forward to your most meritorious response to this humble request.

Thank you and Bravo Baste!

Abba, Khairiyah
Cabamangan, Krystal Rae
Davis, Angela Vera
Ming, Cherry

11/05/2024 @ 4:21p

DR. JAMES D. MARSHALL
REGISTRAR
SAN SEBASTIAN COLLEGE-RECOLETOS
MANILA

Remuneration:

Total # of College Student
SY 2023 - 2024

Look for Eric Chan.

* TOTAL:
749

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Appendix A: Instrument

Instructions: Please answer the following questions honestly. Your responses will remain confidential and used solely for academic purposes. The results of this research will be shared to you through email.

I. Demographic Information

1. Year Level:
 - 1st Year
 - 2nd Year
 - 3rd Year
 - 4th Year
 - Above 4th year
2. Gender:
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to say
3. How many cups of coffee do you drink per day?
 - 0-2 cups
 - 3-5 cups
 - 6-8 cups
 - More than 8 cups
4. I drink matcha at all times.
 - Yes
 - No
5. Do you consume matcha as an alternative to coffee?
 - Yes
 - No
6. Course/Program:
 - BA in Broadcasting (BAB)
 - BA in Communication (BAC)
 - BA in Journalism (BAJ)
 - BA in Political Science (BAPS)
 - BS in Psychology (BSPSY)
 - BS in Accountancy (BSA)
 - BS in Supply Chain Management (BSSCM)
 - BSBA Major in Business Management (BSBA-BM)
 - BSBA Major in Financial Management (BSBA-FM)
 - BSBA Major in Financial and Managerial Accounting (BSBA-FMA)
 - BSBA Major in Human Resource Development Management (BSBA-HRDM)

 - BSBA Major in Legal Management (BSBA-LM)
 - BSBA Major in Marketing Management (BSBA-MM)
 - BS in Computer Science (BSCS)
 - BS in Information Technology (BSIT)
 - BS in Entertainment and Multimedia Computing (BSEMC)
 - BS in Industrial Engineering (BSIE)
 - BS in Exercise and Sports Sciences (BSESS)
 - BS in Hospitality Management (BSHM)
 - BS in Tourism Management (BSTM)
 - Others: (Please specify)

II. Key Factors Influencing Coffee Consumption

7. The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink coffee.
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree
8. I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree
9. I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree
10. I only drink coffee during special circumstances (e.g., midterms or finals).
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree

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11. I drink coffee more frequently than matcha.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

III. Openness to Matcha as an Alternative

12. I am open to trying matcha as an alternative to coffee.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

13. I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

14. I would consider switching from coffee to matcha if more options were available.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

15. Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?

- Yes
- No

IV. Business Opportunities for Coffee and Matcha Near SSC-R Manila

16. Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?

- Yes
- No

17. Do you believe that there are enough matcha shops around SSC-R Manila?

- Yes
- No

18. How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?

- Not Interested at All
- Slightly Interested
- Interested
- Very Interested

19. How interested are you in having more matcha-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?

- Not Interested at All
- Slightly Interested
- Interested
- Very Interested

20. How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?

- Not Likely at All
- Slightly Likely
- Likely
- Very Likely

21. How likely are you to purchase matcha from businesses around SSC-R Manila?

- Not Likely at All
- Slightly Likely
- Likely
- Very Likely

22. How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)?

- Not Likely at All
- Slightly Likely
- Likely
- Very Likely

23. How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila?

- Less than ₱50
- ₱50 to ₱80
- ₱81 to ₱110
- More than ₱110

24. How much are you willing to pay for a cup of matcha around SSC-R Manila?

- Less than ₱50
- ₱50 to ₱80
- ₱81 to ₱110
- More than ₱110

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I drink matcha at all times.

[View options](#) ▾

No

195 responses

Yes

58 responses

Do you consume matcha as an alternative to coffee?

[View options](#) ▾

No

143 responses

Yes

110 responses

The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.

[View options](#) ▾

Agree

147 responses

Strongly agree

78 responses

Disagree

18 responses

Strongly disagree

10 responses

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I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.

[View options](#) ▾

Agree

132 responses

Disagree

65 responses

Strongly agree

49 responses

Strongly disagree

7 responses

I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.

[View options](#) ▾

Agree

139 responses

Strongly agree

102 responses

Strongly disagree

6 responses

Disagree

6 responses

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I only drink coffee during special circumstances such as midterms or finals. [View options](#) ▼

Disagree

81 responses

Agree

75 responses

Strongly disagree

68 responses

Strongly agree

29 responses

I consume coffee more frequently than matcha. [View options](#) ▼

Agree

130 responses

Strongly agree

76 responses

Disagree

35 responses

Strongly disagree

12 responses

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How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals? (e.g, discounts, planners, etc.)

[View options](#) ▾

Likely

118 responses

Very Likely

100 responses

Slightly Likely

32 responses

Not Likely at All

3 responses

I am open to trying matcha as an alternative to coffee.

[View options](#) ▾

Agree

128 responses

Disagree

58 responses

Strongly Agree

46 responses

Strongly Disagree

21 responses

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.

[View options](#) ▾

Agree

120 responses

Strongly Agree

77 responses

Disagree

51 responses

Strongly Disagree

5 responses

I would consider switching from coffee to matcha if more options were available.

[View options](#) ▾

Agree

106 responses

Disagree

88 responses

Strongly Agree

37 responses

Strongly Disagree

22 responses

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?

[View options](#) ▾

No

157 responses

Yes

96 responses

Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?

[View options](#) ▾

Yes

196 responses

No

57 responses

Do you believe that there are enough matcha shops around SSC-R Manila?

[View options](#) ▾

No

187 responses

Yes

66 responses

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?

[View options](#) ▾

Interested

121 responses

Very Interested

65 responses

Slightly Interested

58 responses

Not Interested at All

9 responses

How interested are you in having more matcha-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?

[View options](#) ▾

Interested

92 responses

Slightly Interested

85 responses

Very Interested

41 responses

Not Interested at All

35 responses

How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?

[View options](#) ▾

Likely

145 responses

Very Likely

63 responses

Slightly Likely

37 responses

Not Likely at All

8 responses

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

How likely are you to purchase matcha from businesses around SSC-R Manila? [View options](#)

Likely

93 responses

Slightly Likely

82 responses

Very Likely

40 responses

Not Likely at All

38 responses

How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)? [View options](#)

Very Likely

123 responses

Likely

92 responses

Slightly Likely

33 responses

Not Likely at All

5 responses

How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila? [View options](#)

₱81 to ₱110

117 responses

₱50 to ₱80

83 responses

More than ₱110

46 responses

Less than ₱50

7 responses

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

How much are you willing to pay for a cup of matcha around SSC-R Manila? [View options](#) ▾

- P50 to P80
106 responses
- P81 to P110
82 responses
- Less than P50
34 responses
- More than P110
31 responses

Consent Form

V. Consent ▾ ⋮

Description (optional)

I am invited to participate in this study voluntarily and I give consent to use my responses confidentially. I am also briefed about the purpose of this study and I understand that I have the right to withdraw from this inquiry anytime and that I am not forced by any means by the researchers. *

(By selecting "I Agree" below, you confirm that you have read and understood the purpose of this study and consent to participate.)

I Agree

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

This survey is designed to measure the key factors that motivate College Students at SSC-R Manila to rely on coffee during the Academic Year 2024-2025. It will likewise be useful to determine areas of improvement which will be the basis for enhancing students' academic performance, well-being, and overall experience. The insights gathered will help identify trends in coffee consumption, preferred types of coffee, and the specific reasons students turn to coffee, such as boosting concentration, managing stress, or staying awake for studies.

Please be informed that your personal data and privacy is important to us. As such, any or all personal data you provided will only be used for the purpose stated above. By providing your information to us, you expressly consent to the collection, use and disclosure of your personal information in accordance with this privacy policy. All collected data will be kept secure and confidential, unless otherwise authorized by law. They will be disposed of as soon as the purposes for their use has been achieved. Only aggregate or anonymous data shall be subject to further processing. We respect your rights under the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Should you wish to invoke any such rights in relation to our processing of your personal data, questions or clarifications relative to privacy and data protection, you may contact us at

kl.abbas@sscrmnl.edu.ph

kra.cabamongan@sscrmnl.edu.ph

avmz.dadis@sscrmnl.edu.ph

ct.ming@sscrmnl.edu.ph

V. Consent

 Copy chart

I am invited to participate in this study voluntarily and I give consent to use my responses confidentially. I am also briefed about the purpose of this study and I understand that I have the right to withdraw from this inquiry anytime and that I am not forced by any means by the researchers.

(By selecting "I Agree" below, you confirm that you have read and understood the purpose of this study and consent to participate.)

253 responses

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

Appendix C:

PILOT CRONBACH'S ALPHA

LEGEND	Categories A	Categories B	Categories C	Categories D	CODE
Not Likely at All	Strongly Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not Interested at All	Less than ₱50	1
Slightly Likely	Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Interested	₱50 to ₱80	2
Likely	Agree	Agree	Interested	₱81 to ₱110	3
Very Likely	Strongly Agree	Strongly agree	Very Interested	More than ₱110	4
LEGEND	CODE				
Yes	1				
No	0				
Cronbach's Alpha	Internal consistency				
$0.9 \leq \alpha$	Excellent				
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good				
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable				
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable				
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor				
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable				

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

Key Factors Influencing Coffee Consumption						
CODED Q1	CODED Q2	CODED Q3	CODED Q4	CODED Q5	CODED Q6	
	2	2	2	2	2	4
	3	3	3	2	3	3
	3	3	4	1	2	4
	4	2	3	3	3	3
	3	3	4	4	4	3
	3	4	4	1	4	4
	3	2	3	1	4	4
	4	3	4	3	3	3
	3	3	4	2	3	4
	3	2	3	1	4	3
	3	3	3	2	3	3
	3	3	4	2	4	4
	3	3	3	4	3	3
	4	3	3	4	4	2
	4	3	4	4	2	3
	4	2	4	3	3	3
	3	3	4	3	2	3
	3	2	3	3	2	2
	4	4	4	4	3	4
	3	3	4	3	2	4
	1	2	4	1	4	3
	3	2	3	2	2	4
	4	4	4	4	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	3	4	3
3	3	3	2	3	3
1	2	3	2	3	4
4	1	4	1	4	4
4	3	4	4	4	3
3	4	4	2	4	4
4	2	4	4	1	4
3	3	4	2	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3

STANDARD DEVIATION	0.856074 1225	0.718421 2081	0.567073 6995	1.075759 297	0.856074 1225	0.609071 2125
CHRONBACH'S ALPHA	0.801907 9092	MEANING	Good			

Openness to Matcha as an Alternative			
CODED Q1	CODED Q2	CODED Q3	CODED Q4
3	3	3	1
4	3	3	1
4	3	3	1
1	2	2	0
1	1	1	0
1	2	1	0
1	2	1	0
3	2	3	1

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	2	0
1	3	1	0
3	3	2	0
3	3	2	0
1	1	1	0
3	2	2	0
3	3	3	1
1	2	2	0
3	3	4	1
3	3	3	1
3	3	3	1
4	4	4	1
3	3	2	0
4	2	2	0
4	4	4	1
3	3	3	1
3	3	2	0
1	1	1	1
3	2	2	0
3	3	3	0
2	3	1	0
4	3	4	1
3	4	3	1
3	3	3	1
1.065874622	0.7873751821	0.9755064855	0.5070073487

Business Opportunities for									
----------------------------	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

Coffee and Matcha Near SSC-R Manila	CODE D Q1	CODE D Q2	CODE D Q3	CODE D Q4	CODE D Q5	CODE D Q6	CODE D Q7	CODE D Q8	CODE D Q9	TOTAL
	1	0	3	2	1	1	4	3	1	40
1	0	2	3	4	4	4	3	4	53	
1	0	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	55	
0	0	3	2	3	2	3	4	3	43	
1	0	1	1	1	1	4	2	1	36	
1	0	3	1	3	1	3	2	1	39	
1	0	2	1	3	1	3	4	1	37	
1	0	3	2	3	2	4	2	1	47	
1	0	4	3	3	3	4	4	4	53	
1	0	3	1	3	1	4	3	1	38	
1	0	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	44	
1	0	4	2	3	1	4	2	1	46	
1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	33	
1	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	42	
1	1	3	3	3	3	3	1	2	50	
1	1	2	1	3	1	3	3	1	40	
1	0	2	3	3	4	4	3	3	52	
1	0	1	3	2	3	2	3	3	43	
1	1	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	61	
1	0	3	3	2	2	4	2	4	53	
1	0	3	2	3	2	3	3	2	42	
1	0	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	50	
1	1	4	3	3	3	3	4	3	62	

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	1	2	2	3	3	3	4	3	49
1	1	1	1	2	2	3	2	2	40
0	0	3	4	4	4	4	2	2	42
0	0	4	1	4	1	4	3	3	45
0	0	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	57
1	1	3	1	4	1	4	3	1	46
1	0	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	60
1	1	3	3	3	3	4	2	2	51
1	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	51
0.336	0.470	0.906	1.099	0.877	1.187	0.671	0.859	1.095	
0107	9290	4064	8533	5883	5530	2710	0129	7211	7.5594
525	749	103	63	376	55	62	369	5	41864

FINAL CRONBACH'S ALPHA

LEGEND	Categories A	Categories B	Categories C	Categories D	CODE
Not Likely at All	Strongly Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not Interested at All	Less than ₱50	1
Slightly Likely	Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Interested	₱50 to ₱80	2
Likely	Agree	Agree	Interested	₱81 to ₱110	3
Very Likely	Strongly Agree	Strongly agree	Very Interested	More than ₱110	4
LEGEND	CODE		LEGEND	CODE	
Yes	1		Female	1	
No	0		Male	0	

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

Cronbach's Alpha	Internal consistency		LEGEND	CODE	
$0.9 \leq \alpha$	Excellent		0-2 cups	1	
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good		3-5 cups	2	
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable		6-8 cups	3	
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable		More than 8 cups	4	
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor				
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable				

Key Factors Influencing Coffee Consumption						
	CODED Q1	CODED Q2	CODED Q3	CODED Q4	CODED Q5	CODED Q6
	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	2	3	4	3	3
	4	3	4	4	4	4
	4	1	4	1	4	4
	3	3	4	2	4	4
	4	4	4	1	4	3
	3	3	3	2	3	4
	3	4	4	1	1	2
	3	3	3	2	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	4	3	3	4	4
3	2	4	1	1	3
3	3	3	3	3	2
4	2	4	4	1	3
3	2	3	2	3	1
4	3	4	4	4	3
4	2	4	1	4	4
3	3	3	1	3	4
4	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	2	4	4
3	4	4	4	4	4
3	3	1	3	1	3
3	3	4	1	4	3
3	2	4	2	3	3
3	3	4	1	4	3
2	2	3	4	2	3
1	2	3	4	4	3
2	4	3	2	3	2
4	1	4	2	4	3
2	3	4	1	4	2
4	3	4	1	3	3
4	2	3	2	4	3
3	4	4	3	3	4
4	2	3	1	3	4
3	3	3	3	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	2	2	2	2	3
4	2	4	1	4	4
3	3	4	3	3	3
4	4	4	2	4	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	2	4	3	1	4
4	2	3	1	2	4
4	2	3	2	4	2
4	2	3	3	2	4
3	3	3	4	4	4
4	2	3	3	2	2
4	2	3	3	2	3
2	3	3	3	2	4
3	3	3	3	3	3
4	3	3	3	4	3
3	3	4	2	2	3
3	2	3	3	3	4
3	3	4	1	4	4
3	3	3	2	2	3
4	3	4	1	4	4
3	2	3	2	3	3
3	2	4	2	3	3
4	3	3	4	4	2
3	3	2	2	3	3
1	2	1	1	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	3	1	2
3	4	3	3	3	3
4	2	4	2	4	3
3	3	3	3	4	4
4	4	4	3	3	4
4	3	4	2	3	4
4	4	4	3	3	4
4	4	3	2	4	4
4	4	4	3	4	4
3	3	3	1	4	3
4	4	4	2	4	4
3	3	4	1	3	3
4	4	4	4	4	4
3	3	3	1	3	3
4	4	4	1	3	4
4	2	3	1	3	3
3	3	3	1	3	2
1	3	1	3	1	4
4	4	4	2	4	3
3	3	3	1	3	2
4	4	4	2	3	4
4	4	4	1	3	3
3	3	3	2	2	3
4	4	3	2	3	2
4	4	3	1	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	4	2	4	4
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	2	3	3
4	4	3	1	2	4
4	4	4	2	3	4
4	4	4	1	3	4
3	3	4	2	3	3
3	3	4	1	3	3
3	3	4	2	2	4
4	4	3	2	3	4
3	3	3	1	3	3
4	4	4	1	3	4
3	3	3	1	3	4
3	3	3	3	3	3
4	4	4	1	3	4
3	3	4	2	3	4
3	3	3	2	3	4
4	4	4	2	3	4
3	3	3	2	3	3
3	3	3	1	3	4
3	3	4	4	4	3
3	3	3	1	4	3
4	4	4	1	3	4
3	3	4	1	3	4
3	3	2	2	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	4	1	3	3
4	4	4	1	4	4
4	1	4	1	3	4
3	2	3	2	3	3
3	2	4	2	3	3
3	4	3	2	4	3
4	3	3	2	4	2
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4	3	4	1	4	4
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4	2	3	2	4	2
3	2	3	3	2	4
3	2	3	3	3	2
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	2
3	3	3	3	4	2
4	4	4	4	3	4
3	3	3	4	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	2	2	3
3	3	4	4	3	3
3	3	3	2	3	3
4	2	4	2	3	3
3	3	4	2	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
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3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	4	3
3	3	3	4	4	2
3	3	3	3	3	3
4	4	4	1	4	4
2	3	4	2	3	4
1	1	1	1	1	3
3	2	3	3	3	3
3	3	4	2	3	3
2	3	3	4	4	4
3	2	3	2	3	4
2	3	3	3	1	2
3	2	2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	3	3	3
3	4	3	1	4	4
3	2	4	2	4	3
3	4	3	1	4	3
3	2	3	3	2	3
2	3	3	3	2	2
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2	3	3	2	3	4
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	4
3	3	3	3	3	2
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	2	3	3
3	3	3	2	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	2	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	2	3	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	4	4	1	3	3
3	2	3	2	4	2
4	3	3	1	4	3
4	4	3	1	4	4
3	3	3	1	4	2
3	4	4	1	4	4
4	2	4	1	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	2	4	1	3	3
3	3	4	3	4	4
3	4	4	3	4	4
4	3	4	3	4	4
4	3	4	3	4	4
3	3	3	3	3	4
2	3	3	3	3	4
2	3	3	3	3	4
3	2	3	3	2	4
3	2	4	2	3	4
2	3	3	3	2	2
4	4	3	1	4	3
4	2	4	1	3	4
3	3	3	2	3	3
3	2	4	2	4	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4	4	4
3	3	3	4	3	3
4	4	3	1	3	4
3	2	4	1	3	3
3	2	3	3	2	2
3	2	3	2	3	3
2	3	3	3	2	2
3	2	3	2	3	4
3	2	3	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	2	4	2	2	3
3	3	3	3	3	3
3	2	3	1	3	4
3	3	3	3	3	2
3	2	3	2	3	3
3	3	3	2	2	3
3	3	3	2	3	4
2	2	2	2	2	1
3	3	3	2	3	2
3	3	3	2	2	4

MEAN	3.168949 772	2.904109 589	3.310502 283	2.219178 082	3.059360 731	3.223744 292
STANDARD DEVIATION	0.699766 863	0.744971 8342	0.631315 231	0.961362 403	0.784682 2255	0.729573 6146
CRONBACH'S ALPHA	0.769291 5505	MEANING	Acceptable			

Openness to Matcha as an Alternative				
CODED Q1	CODED Q2	CODED Q3	CODED Q4	
4	4	4	0	
3	3	2	0	
4	3	4	1	

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	4	0
3	3	3	1
2	2	2	0
3	2	3	1
2	4	3	0
3	3	2	0
3	3	4	1
4	2	4	1
3	3	3	1
4	4	4	1
1	1	1	0
3	3	3	0
2	2	2	0
3	3	3	1
2	2	2	0
2	3	1	0
3	3	2	0
2	2	2	0
2	2	2	0
3	3	3	0
2	3	2	0
4	4	4	1
2	2	3	1
2	2	3	0
3	3	4	1

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	2	2	0
4	3	4	0
1	1	1	0
4	2	3	1
3	3	2	0
4	3	3	1
4	3	3	1
3	2	2	0
3	3	2	0
2	2	2	0
3	3	3	1
4	4	4	1
4	4	4	1
1	2	1	0
4	3	3	1
3	3	2	0
4	4	4	1
4	4	4	1
3	3	3	1
3	4	3	1
2	3	2	0
3	3	3	1
2	2	2	0
4	4	4	1
3	3	3	1

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	2	1	0
2	2	2	0
4	3	3	0
1	3	2	0
2	2	2	0
4	2	1	0
2	3	2	0
3	3	3	1
2	3	2	0
3	4	3	1
3	4	2	0
3	4	2	0
3	4	3	1
2	3	2	0
3	3	3	0
1	3	1	0
3	4	2	0
2	3	2	0
3	4	3	0
3	4	2	0
4	4	3	1
3	4	2	0
3	4	2	0
4	2	1	0
2	2	2	0

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	2	0
3	4	3	1
2	3	2	0
1	4	1	0
3	4	3	0
2	4	2	0
4	4	3	1
1	3	2	0
1	3	1	0
3	4	3	1
4	4	3	0
2	4	2	0
3	4	2	0
3	4	2	0
3	3	3	1
3	4	2	0
3	4	2	0
3	4	3	0
4	4	3	1
2	4	2	0
3	4	3	1
3	4	3	0
3	4	3	0
3	4	2	0
2	4	2	0

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	4	3	0
2	4	3	0
2	4	2	0
4	4	4	1
4	4	4	1
3	4	3	1
3	4	2	0
3	4	3	0
4	4	4	1
3	3	2	0
3	4	4	0
2	4	2	0
1	4	1	0
4	3	4	1
3	3	2	0
4	3	4	1
4	2	3	1
3	4	1	0
4	4	4	1
4	4	4	1
4	4	4	1
2	4	2	0
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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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0.801218125	0.7447468692	0.8164452725	0.4838734002

Business Opportunities for Coffee and									
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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

Matcha Near SSC-R Manila	CODE	TOTAL								
	D Q1	D Q2	D Q3	D Q4	D Q5	D Q6	D Q7	D Q8	D Q9	
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	1	0	1	4	4	4	4	2	3	54
	1	1	4	4	2	4	3	4	4	52
	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	41
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	1	0	3	2	3	3	4	2	2	51

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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1	0	2	2	2	2	2	4	4	48

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0.757	0.251	2.981	2.575	3.050	2.552	3.296	2.794	2.452	
9908	1415	7351	3424	2283	5114	8036	5205	0547	47.552
676	525	6	66	11	16	53	48	95	51142
0.429	0.434	0.772	0.897	0.698	0.893	0.788	0.753	0.841	
2810	6632	0072	2609	7783	7759	9947	4429	1617	6.2435
075	917	153	935	855	266	226	374	549	82437

RQ1 TREATMENTS

	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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SUMMARY OUTPUT								
SUMMARY OUTPUT								
SUMMARY OUTPUT								
SUMMARY OUTPUT	8.4178							
SUMMARY OUTPUT	98998							
SUMMARY OUTPUT								
Residual Dev.	295.17							
	59999							

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# of iterations	5							
Observations	219							
	Coefficients	Standard Error	P-value	Odds Ratio	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95%	Upper 95%
Intercept	-2.514916614	0.942102862	0.007597075048	0.08086965533	0.01276045564	0.5125131372	0.01276045564	0.5125131372
The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	0.3168673234	0.2360795332	0.1795292699	1.372820419	0.8642959284	2.180544695	0.8642959284	2.180544695
I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its	0.1305794468	0.1934141386	0.4995939655	1.139488465	0.7799657277	1.664732072	0.7799657277	1.664732072

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quality or taste.									
I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.	0.3375 81386 4	0.2636 04667 1	0.2003 21869 1	1.4015 53671	0.8360 43806 3	2.3495 8106	0.8360 43806 3	2.3495 8106	

Correlation Range Condition (Value in G225)	Example Description Text
CORREL < -1	Invalid Correlation: Value < -1
CORREL = -1	Perfect Negative Relationship

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$-1 < \text{CORREL} \leq -0.7$	Strong Negative Relationship
$-0.7 < \text{CORREL} \leq -0.4$	Moderate Negative Relationship
$-0.4 < \text{CORREL} \leq -0.1$	Weak Negative Relationship
$-0.1 < \text{CORREL} < 0.1$	Negligible Relationship
$0.1 \leq \text{CORREL} < 0.4$	Weak Positive Relationship
$0.4 \leq \text{CORREL} < 0.7$	Moderate Positive Relationship
$0.7 \leq \text{CORREL} < 1$	Strong Positive Relationship
$\text{CORREL} = 1$	Perfect Positive Relationship
$\text{CORREL} > 1$	Invalid Correlation: Value > 1

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How many cups of coffee do you drink per day?	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
1	1	1	1
1	2	2	3
1	4	3	4
2	4	1	4
1	3	3	4
3	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	3	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	2	4	3
2	3	2	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	2	4
1	3	2	3
1	4	3	4
1	4	2	4

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1	3	3	3
2	4	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	4	4
1	3	3	1
2	3	3	4
1	3	2	4
1	3	3	4
1	2	2	3
2	1	2	3
1	2	4	3
2	4	1	4
2	2	3	4
1	4	3	4
1	4	2	3
1	3	4	4
1	4	2	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	2	2
1	4	2	4
1	3	3	4
1	4	4	4
2	3	3	3
1	3	2	4
2	4	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	2	3
1	4	2	3
1	3	3	3
1	4	2	3
1	4	2	3
1	2	3	3
2	3	3	3
1	4	3	3
1	3	3	4
1	3	2	3
4	3	3	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	3	4
1	3	2	3
1	3	2	4
1	4	3	3
2	3	3	2
1	1	2	1
1	1	3	3
1	3	4	3
1	4	2	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	4	3	4
1	4	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	4	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	4
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	4	2	3
1	3	3	3
1	1	3	1
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	3
1	4	4	3
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	3
2	4	4	4
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	4
1	3	3	4
1	4	4	3
1	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	4
2	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
2	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	4
2	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	4
1	3	3	2
2	4	4	4
2	4	4	4
2	4	1	4
1	3	2	3
1	3	2	4
2	3	4	3
2	4	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	4
1	4	3	4
2	3	4	4
1	1	1	3
1	3	4	3
1	4	2	4
1	4	2	4
1	4	3	4
2	4	3	4
1	3	3	3
3	4	2	3
1	3	2	3
2	3	2	3
3	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	3	3	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	2	4
1	3	3	4
2	3	3	3
1	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
1	2	3	4
1	1	1	1
2	3	2	3
2	3	3	4
3	2	3	3
2	3	2	3
1	2	3	3
1	3	2	2
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	3	4	3
2	3	2	4
2	3	4	3
2	3	2	3
1	2	3	3
3	3	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	2	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	3	4	4
1	3	2	3
2	4	3	3
2	4	4	3
1	3	3	3
2	3	4	4
2	4	2	4
1	4	2	4
2	3	3	4
1	3	4	4
1	4	3	4
1	4	3	4
1	3	3	3
2	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	2	3	3
2	3	2	3
3	3	2	4
1	2	3	3
2	4	4	3
2	4	2	4
2	3	3	3
2	3	2	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
2	4	4	3
1	3	2	4
1	3	2	3
2	3	2	3
1	2	3	3
3	3	2	3
2	3	2	3
1	3	2	4
1	3	3	3
2	3	2	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	2	3
2	3	3	3
1	3	3	3

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	1	2	2	2
	2	3	3	3
	2	3	3	3
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.042910993	0.000579958	0.086401694	
N	69	9923	43	
MEANING	Negligible Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Negligible Relationship	

I only drink coffee during special circumstances such as midterms or finals.	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
	1	1	1
	4	2	2
	4	4	3
	1	4	1
	2	3	3
	1	4	4
	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	4	4
2	3	3	3
3	2	4	3
1	3	2	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	2	4
2	3	2	3
4	4	3	4
1	4	2	4
1	3	3	3
3	4	3	3
2	3	3	3
4	3	4	4
3	3	3	1
1	3	3	4
2	3	2	4
1	3	3	4
4	2	2	3
4	1	2	3
2	2	4	3
2	4	1	4
1	2	3	4
1	4	3	4
2	4	2	3
3	3	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	2	3
3	3	3	3
2	3	2	2
1	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
2	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	3	2	4
1	4	2	3
2	4	2	3
3	4	2	3
4	3	3	3
3	4	2	3
3	4	2	3
3	2	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	4	3	3
2	3	3	4
3	3	2	3
1	3	3	4
2	3	3	3
1	4	3	4
2	3	2	3
2	3	2	4
4	4	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	3	3	2
1	1	2	1
3	1	3	3
3	3	4	3
2	4	2	4
3	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
2	4	3	4
3	4	4	4
2	4	4	3
3	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	4
4	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	4	2	3
1	3	3	3
3	1	3	1
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
1	4	4	4
2	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	4	4	3
1	4	4	3
2	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
1	4	4	3
2	4	4	4
1	4	4	4
2	3	3	4
1	3	3	4
2	3	3	4
2	4	4	3
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
2	3	3	4
2	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
2	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
4	3	3	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	4
2	3	3	2
1	4	4	4
1	4	4	4
1	4	1	4
2	3	2	3
2	3	2	4
2	3	4	3
2	4	3	3
4	3	3	4
1	4	3	4
4	3	4	4
2	1	1	3
2	3	4	3
1	4	2	4
1	4	2	4
1	4	3	4
1	4	3	4
4	3	3	3
2	4	2	3
3	3	2	3
3	3	2	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	4	4
4	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
4	3	3	4
2	3	3	3
2	4	2	4
2	3	3	4
3	3	3	3
3	2	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
4	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
2	2	3	4
1	1	1	1
3	3	2	3
2	3	3	4
4	2	3	3
2	3	2	3
3	2	3	3
2	3	2	2
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
1	3	4	3
2	3	2	4
1	3	4	3
3	3	2	3
3	2	3	3
2	3	2	3
2	2	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
1	3	4	4
2	3	2	3
1	4	3	3
1	4	4	3
1	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	4	4
1	4	2	4
1	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
3	3	4	4
3	4	3	4
3	4	3	4
3	3	3	3
3	2	3	3
3	2	3	3
3	3	2	3
2	3	2	4
3	2	3	3
1	4	4	3
1	4	2	4
2	3	3	3
2	3	2	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
4	3	3	3
1	4	4	3
1	3	2	4
3	3	2	3
2	3	2	3
3	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	3	2	3
3	3	2	3
2	3	2	4
3	3	3	3
1	3	2	3
3	3	3	3
2	3	2	3
2	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
	-0.225765091	0.023075409	-0.127762206
	1	01	9
	Weak Negative Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Weak Negative Relationship

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I consume coffee more frequently than matcha.	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
1	1	1	1
3	2	2	3
4	4	3	4
4	4	1	4
4	3	3	4
4	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
1	3	4	4
3	3	3	3
4	2	4	3
1	3	2	4
3	3	3	3
1	4	2	4
3	3	2	3
4	4	3	4
4	4	2	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	3
3	4	3	3
4	3	3	3
4	3	4	4
1	3	3	1
4	3	3	4
3	3	2	4
4	3	3	4
2	2	2	3
4	1	2	3
3	2	4	3
4	4	1	4
4	2	3	4
3	4	3	4
4	4	2	3
3	3	4	4
3	4	2	3
2	3	3	3
2	3	2	2
4	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
4	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
1	3	2	4
2	4	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	2	3
2	4	2	3
4	3	3	3
2	4	2	3
2	4	2	3
2	2	3	3
3	3	3	3
4	4	3	3
2	3	3	4
3	3	2	3
4	3	3	4
2	3	3	3
4	4	3	4
3	3	2	3
3	3	2	4
4	4	3	3
3	3	3	2
3	1	2	1
1	1	3	3
3	3	4	3
4	4	2	4
4	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	4	3	4
3	4	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	4	3
4	4	4	4
4	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
3	3	3	4
4	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	4	2	3
3	3	3	3
1	1	3	1
4	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	4	4	4
2	3	3	3
3	4	4	3
3	4	4	3
4	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
2	4	4	3
3	4	4	4
3	4	4	4
3	3	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	4
2	3	3	4
3	4	4	3
3	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	3	3	4
3	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
4	3	3	4
4	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	3	3	4
3	3	3	2
3	4	4	4
4	4	4	4
3	4	1	4
3	3	2	3
3	3	2	4
4	3	4	3
4	4	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	4
4	4	3	4
4	3	4	4
2	1	1	3
3	3	4	3
4	4	2	4
4	4	2	4
3	4	3	4
4	4	3	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	2	3
2	3	2	3
3	3	2	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
4	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
3	3	3	4
3	3	3	3
3	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
3	3	3	3
3	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
4	3	3	3
4	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
3	2	3	4
1	1	1	1
3	3	2	3
3	3	3	4
4	2	3	3
3	3	2	3
1	2	3	3
2	3	2	2
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
4	3	4	3
4	3	2	4
4	3	4	3
2	3	2	3
2	2	3	3
2	3	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	2	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	4	4
4	3	2	3
4	4	3	3
4	4	4	3
4	3	3	3
4	3	4	4
3	4	2	4
3	4	2	4
4	3	3	4
4	3	4	4
4	4	3	4
4	4	3	4
3	3	3	3
3	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	2	3	3
2	3	2	3
3	3	2	4
2	2	3	3
4	4	4	3
3	4	2	4
3	3	3	3
4	3	2	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	4	4	3
3	3	2	4
2	3	2	3
3	3	2	3
2	2	3	3
3	3	2	3
3	3	2	3
2	3	2	4
3	3	3	3
3	3	2	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	2	3
2	3	3	3
3	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3
2	3	3	3
	0.382645344	0.260889592	0.360795452
	6	3	4
	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship

RQ2 TREATMENTS

I am open to trying matcha as an alternative to coffee.	I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.
4	4
3	3
4	3
4	4
3	3
2	2
3	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	4
3	3
3	3
4	2
3	3
4	4
1	1
3	3
2	2
3	3
2	2
2	3
3	3
2	2
2	2
3	3
2	3
4	4
2	2
2	2
3	3
2	2
4	3
1	1
4	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3
4	3
4	3
3	2
3	3
2	2
3	3
4	4
4	4
1	2
4	3
3	3
4	4
4	4
3	3
3	4
2	3
3	3
2	2
4	4
3	3
1	2
2	2
4	3
1	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	2
4	2
2	3
3	3
2	3
3	4
3	4
3	4
3	4
2	3
3	3
1	3
3	4
2	3
3	4
3	4
4	4
3	4
3	4
4	2
2	2
1	3
3	4
2	3
1	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	4
2	4
4	4
1	3
1	3
3	4
4	4
2	4
3	4
3	4
3	3
3	4
3	4
3	4
4	4
2	4
3	4
3	4
3	4
3	4
2	4
3	4
2	4
2	4
4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4
3	4
3	4
3	4
4	4
3	3
3	4
2	4
1	4
4	3
3	3
4	3
4	2
3	4
4	4
4	4
4	4
2	4
3	3
2	2
4	4
2	2
3	3
3	3
3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3
3	3
3	3
3	4
3	3
4	4
3	4
4	3
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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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SPEARMAN'S CORRELATIO N	0.384268741 7
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

I am open to trying matcha as an alternative to coffee.	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
4	1	1	1
3	2	2	3
4	4	3	4
4	4	1	4
3	3	3	4
2	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
2	3	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	2	4	3
4	3	2	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	2	4
1	3	2	3
3	4	3	4
2	4	2	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	3
2	4	3	3
2	3	3	3
3	3	4	4
2	3	3	1
2	3	3	4
3	3	2	4
2	3	3	4
4	2	2	3
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2	2	4	3
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2	2	3	4
4	4	3	4
1	4	2	3
4	3	4	4
3	4	2	3
4	3	3	3
4	3	2	2
3	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
2	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
4	3	2	4
4	4	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	2	3
4	4	2	3
3	3	3	3
4	4	2	3
4	4	2	3
3	2	3	3
3	3	3	3
2	4	3	3
3	3	3	4
2	3	2	3
4	3	3	4
3	3	3	3
1	4	3	4
2	3	2	3
4	3	2	4
1	4	3	3
2	3	3	2
4	1	2	1
2	1	3	3
3	3	4	3
2	4	2	4
3	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
3	4	3	4
3	4	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	4	4	3
3	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
2	3	3	4
3	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
3	4	2	3
3	3	3	3
4	1	3	1
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
2	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
3	4	4	3
2	4	4	3
4	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
3	4	4	3
4	4	4	4
2	4	4	4
3	3	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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3	3	3	4
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3	4	4	4
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2	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
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3	3	3	2
3	4	4	4
3	4	4	4
4	4	1	4
3	3	2	3
3	3	2	4
2	3	4	3
1	4	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	3	3	4
3	4	3	4
4	3	4	4
4	1	1	3
3	3	4	3
4	4	2	4
4	4	2	4
4	4	3	4
2	4	3	4
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4	3	2	3
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3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
4	3	3	3
3	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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2	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
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3	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
3	2	3	4
3	1	1	1
2	3	2	3
3	3	3	4
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3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
2	3	4	3
2	3	2	4
1	3	4	3
2	3	2	3
3	2	3	3
2	3	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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3	3	3	3
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3	3	4	4
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4	4	2	4
3	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
3	3	4	4
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3	3	3	3
3	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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2	4	4	3
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3	3	3	3
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2	3	3	3
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3	3	2	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

	2	2	2	2
	2	3	3	3
	3	3	3	3
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATIO N	0.008966160 218	-0.12317310 5	0.127334908 1	
MEANING	Negligible Relationship	Weak Negative Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	

I would consider switching from coffee to matcha if more options were available.	I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.
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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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SPEARMAN'S CORRELATIO N	0.368937752 3
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

I would consider switching from coffee to matcha if more options were available.	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
4	1	1	1
2	2	2	3
4	4	3	4
4	4	1	4
3	3	3	4
2	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
3	3	4	4
2	3	3	3
4	2	4	3
4	3	2	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	2	4
1	3	2	3
3	4	3	4
2	4	2	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	3
2	4	3	3
1	3	3	3
2	3	4	4
2	3	3	1
2	3	3	4
3	3	2	4
2	3	3	4
4	2	2	3
3	1	2	3
3	2	4	3
4	4	1	4
2	2	3	4
4	4	3	4
1	4	2	3
3	3	4	4
2	4	2	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	2	2
2	4	2	4
2	3	3	4
2	4	4	4
3	3	3	3
4	3	2	4
4	4	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	2	3
3	4	2	3
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3	3	3	3
1	4	3	4
2	3	2	3
3	3	2	4
2	4	3	3
2	3	3	2
1	1	2	1
2	1	3	3
3	3	4	3
2	4	2	4
3	3	3	3
2	4	4	4
2	4	3	4
3	4	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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2	3	3	3
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2	4	4	4
2	3	3	3
3	4	4	4
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2	4	4	3
3	4	4	4
2	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
3	4	4	3
3	4	4	4
2	4	4	4
2	3	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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3	4	4	4
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2	3	3	3
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4	3	3	4
3	3	3	2
2	4	4	4
3	4	4	4
4	4	1	4
2	3	2	3
4	3	2	4
2	3	4	3
1	4	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	3	3	4
2	4	3	4
4	3	4	4
3	1	1	3
1	3	4	3
4	4	2	4
4	4	2	4
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3	3	2	3
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3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
3	3	3	3
3	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
2	2	3	4
2	1	1	1
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2	3	4	3
2	3	2	4
2	3	4	3
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3	2	3	3
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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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4	4	2	4
4	4	2	4
3	3	3	4
4	3	4	4
3	4	3	4
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3	3	3	3
3	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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2	4	4	3
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3	3	2	3
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2	3	3	3
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2	3	3	3
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3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

	2	2	2	2
	2	3	3	3
	3	3	3	3
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATIO N	0.061592555 24	-0.15228292 07	0.207250803	
MEANING	Negligible Relationship	Weak Negative Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	

Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?	I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.
0	4
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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	3
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SPEARMAN'S CORRELATIO N	0.221279832 4
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
0	1	1	1
0	2	2	3
1	4	3	4
0	4	1	4
1	3	3	4
0	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
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0	3	3	3
1	2	4	3
1	3	2	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	2	4
0	3	2	3
0	4	3	4
0	4	2	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	3
0	4	3	3
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1	2	2	3
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1	4	1	4
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1	3	3	3
1	3	2	2
0	4	2	4
0	3	3	4
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1	3	3	3
1	3	2	4
1	4	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	4	2	3
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0	3	3	3
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0	3	3	2
0	1	2	1
0	1	3	3
1	3	4	3
0	4	2	4
1	3	3	3
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0	4	3	4
1	4	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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0	4	4	4
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0	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
0	4	2	3
0	3	3	3
0	1	3	1
0	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
0	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
0	4	4	3
0	4	4	3
1	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	3
0	4	4	4
0	4	4	4
0	3	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	3	3	4
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0	4	4	3
0	3	3	3
0	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
0	3	3	4
0	3	3	3
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1	3	3	2
0	4	4	4
0	4	4	4
1	4	1	4
0	3	2	3
0	3	2	4
0	3	4	3
0	4	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	4
0	4	3	4
1	3	4	4
1	1	1	3
0	3	4	3
1	4	2	4
1	4	2	4
1	4	3	4
0	4	3	4
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0	4	2	3
1	3	2	3
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0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	3	3	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	2	4
0	3	3	4
1	3	3	3
0	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	4	4	4
0	2	3	4
0	1	1	1
0	3	2	3
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0	2	3	3
1	3	2	2
0	3	3	3
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0	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
0	3	4	3
0	3	2	4
0	3	4	3
0	3	2	3
1	2	3	3
0	3	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	2	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
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1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
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1	3	4	4
0	3	2	3
0	4	3	3
0	4	4	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	4	4
1	4	2	4
1	4	2	4
1	3	3	4
1	3	4	4
1	4	3	4
1	4	3	4
0	3	3	3
1	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	2	3	3
1	3	2	3
0	3	2	4
1	2	3	3
0	4	4	3
1	4	2	4
0	3	3	3
0	3	2	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	3
1	3	2	4
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1	2	3	3
0	3	2	3
0	3	2	3
0	3	2	4
0	3	3	3
0	3	2	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	2	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

	0	2	2	2
	0	3	3	3
	0	3	3	3
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATIO N	0.017815858 63	-0.02841427 955	0.117868363 2	
MEANING	Negligible Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	

Do you consume matcha as an alternative to coffee?	I believe matcha provides similar benefits to coffee in terms of energy and focus.
0	4
0	3
0	3
0	4
0	3
0	2
0	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	4
0	3
0	3
1	2
0	3
0	4
0	1
1	3
1	2
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0	2
1	3
0	3
1	4
0	2
0	2
1	3
0	2
1	3
0	1
1	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	3
1	3
1	3
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1	4
1	4
0	2
1	3
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1	4
1	4
1	3
0	4
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1	3
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1	4
1	3
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0	3
0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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1	2
0	2
0	3
1	4
0	3
0	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

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0	4
1	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4
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1	3
1	4
0	4
0	4
1	3
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1	2
0	4
1	4
1	4
1	4
0	4
1	3
0	2
0	4
0	2
0	3
0	3
1	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3
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1	4
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1	3
0	3
0	3
0	3
1	3
0	3
0	3
0	2
1	2
0	3
0	2
1	3
0	2
0	2
0	3
1	3
0	3
1	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3
0	3
1	3
0	3
0	3
0	4
0	2
1	3
0	2
0	3
1	3
1	3
0	3
0	3
0	3
0	3
0	3
0	3
1	3
0	2
0	3
1	4
0	3
0	4
0	3
0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4
1	4
1	4
1	3
1	3
1	3
1	4
0	3
0	3
0	2
1	3
0	2
1	3
0	3
1	4
1	3
1	4
0	3
1	3
1	3
1	4
1	4
1	3
0	2
1	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	2
0	3
1	2
0	2
0	2
0	2
1	3
1	3
1	3
0	2
1	2
0	2
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATIO N	0.294139883 6
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship

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San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

Do you see yourself switching from coffee to matcha in the next five years?	The quality of coffee is one of the most important factors that influence me to drink it.	I always consider the affordability of the coffee rather than its quality or taste.	I have my own preference (e.g., strong, sweet, and balanced, environmental sustainability) when buying coffee.
0	1	1	1
0	2	2	3
0	4	3	4
0	4	1	4
0	3	3	4
0	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
0	3	4	4
0	3	3	3
0	2	4	3
1	3	2	4
0	3	3	3
0	4	2	4
0	3	2	3
1	4	3	4
1	4	2	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	3
0	4	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	4	4
0	3	3	1
0	3	3	4
1	3	2	4
0	3	3	4
1	2	2	3
0	1	2	3
0	2	4	3
1	4	1	4
0	2	3	4
1	4	3	4
0	4	2	3
1	3	4	4
0	4	2	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	2	2
0	4	2	4
0	3	3	4
0	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
1	3	2	4
1	4	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	4	2	3
1	4	2	3
0	3	3	3
1	4	2	3
1	4	2	3
1	2	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	4	3	3
1	3	3	4
0	3	2	3
1	3	3	4
1	3	3	3
0	4	3	4
0	3	2	3
0	3	2	4
0	4	3	3
0	3	3	2
1	1	2	1
0	1	3	3
0	3	4	3
0	4	2	4
1	3	3	3
0	4	4	4
0	4	3	4
1	4	4	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	4	4	3
1	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
0	3	3	4
1	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
0	4	4	4
0	4	2	3
0	3	3	3
1	1	3	1
0	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
0	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
0	4	4	3
0	4	4	3
1	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	3
1	4	4	4
0	4	4	4
1	3	3	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	3	3	4
1	3	3	4
1	4	4	3
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	4
1	3	3	2
1	4	4	4
1	4	4	4
1	4	1	4
1	3	2	3
1	3	2	4
0	3	4	3
0	4	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	4
0	4	3	4
0	3	4	4
1	1	1	3
0	3	4	3
1	4	2	4
1	4	2	4
1	4	3	4
0	4	3	4
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0	3	2	3
0	3	2	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
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0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	3	3	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	2	4
1	3	3	4
1	3	3	3
0	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	4	4	4
1	2	3	4
0	1	1	1
0	3	2	3
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0	2	3	3
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0	3	3	3
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0	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
0	3	4	3
0	3	2	4
0	3	4	3
0	3	2	3
1	2	3	3
0	3	2	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	2	3	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
0	3	3	3
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1	3	4	4
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0	4	3	3
0	4	4	3
0	3	3	3
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1	4	2	4
1	4	2	4
1	3	3	4
1	3	4	4
1	4	3	4
1	4	3	4
0	3	3	3
0	2	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

0	2	3	3
1	3	2	3
0	3	2	4
1	2	3	3
0	4	4	3
1	4	2	4
1	3	3	3
1	3	2	4
0	3	3	3
1	4	4	4
1	3	3	3
1	4	4	3
1	3	2	4
1	3	2	3
0	3	2	3
1	2	3	3
0	3	2	3
0	3	2	3
0	3	2	3
0	3	3	3
1	3	2	3
1	3	3	3
1	3	3	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

	0	2	2	2
	1	3	3	3
	0	3	3	3
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATIO N	0.104911343 5	-0.01103752 775	0.226762147 9	
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship	Negligible Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	

RQ3 TREATMENTS

How many cups of coffee do you drink per day?	How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)?	How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?	How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?	Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?	How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila?
1	1	1	2	0	4
1	2	2	1	1	2
1	4	4	4	1	3
2	4	4	3	1	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	2	2	1	4
3	4	4	3	1	2
1	4	3	2	1	3
1	2	2	2	0	2
1	4	3	2	1	1
1	4	4	1	1	2
2	3	2	4	1	4
1	2	2	2	0	2
1	4	3	2	1	3
1	1	1	2	1	2
1	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	4	4	1	4
1	4	3	2	1	3
2	4	4	4	1	3
1	4	4	2	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	2
1	3	3	3	1	4
2	4	2	3	1	3
1	2	2	2	1	2
1	3	3	4	1	3
1	3	3	4	1	4
2	3	3	3	1	3
1	2	3	2	0	2
2	4	4	4	1	3
2	2	3	3	1	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	2	3	1	4
1	3	3	3	1	4
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	3	3	4	1	4
1	3	3	4	0	4
1	3	2	3	1	2
1	4	4	4	1	4
1	3	2	2	1	2
1	4	4	3	1	3
2	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	4
2	4	4	4	1	4
1	4	3	3	1	4
1	4	4	4	0	2
1	4	3	2	1	1
1	2	2	2	1	4
1	3	2	1	1	4
1	4	3	3	0	3
2	4	3	3	1	1
1	4	3	3	1	2
1	3	3	2	1	4
1	3	3	3	1	4
4	4	4	4	1	2
1	3	3	3	1	2
1	4	4	4	1	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	3	3	1	3
1	3	3	3	0	3
1	1	1	1	1	2
2	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	4	4	1	3
1	1	1	1	1	1
1	3	2	3	1	2
1	3	3	2	1	3
1	3	2	4	1	3
1	4	4	3	1	4
1	4	4	4	1	4
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	4	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	4	1	4
1	3	3	3	1	4
2	4	4	4	1	2
1	3	2	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	2	2	2	1	4
1	4	3	4	1	3
1	4	4	4	0	3
1	4	4	3	1	3
1	3	2	3	0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	4	0	3
1	3	3	3	0	2
1	3	3	4	0	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	4	4	0	3
1	4	4	3	1	2
1	3	3	3	1	2
1	4	4	4	0	3
2	4	3	4	1	2
2	4	3	3	0	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	2	2	0	3
1	4	3	2	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	4	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	2
2	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	0	2
2	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	4	1	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	3	3	0	2
2	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	3	3	3	1	2
2	3	4	4	0	3
2	4	3	4	1	3
2	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
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1	2	3	3	1	2
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1	3	4	3	1	4
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1	3	4	4	0	3
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1	4	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	3	1	2
1	2	3	2	0	2
3	2	2	3	0	3
1	4	3	4	1	2
2	4	4	3	0	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	3	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	2	1	2
1	2	3	3	1	3
1	2	4	3	1	3
1	2	4	3	1	3
1	3	3	2	1	2
2	3	4	4	1	4
1	2	2	2	1	2
1	3	3	4	1	3
1	3	3	4	1	2
2	2	3	2	1	4
1	3	3	2	1	3
1	2	2	2	1	2
1	3	3	2	1	2
2	3	3	3	1	4
2	3	3	2	1	3
1	4	3	2	1	2
2	4	4	4	1	4
1	4	3	3	0	4
1	2	2	2	1	2
2	4	4	3	0	2
2	3	3	3	0	2
3	3	3	3	0	3
2	4	4	4	0	2
1	3	3	3	1	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	2	2	2	0	2
1	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	4
1	2	3	2	1	3
1	3	3	2	1	3
1	4	3	2	1	3
2	4	4	3	1	2
2	4	4	4	1	3
2	4	4	4	1	3
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1	2	2	2	0	2
3	4	4	4	0	3
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1	4	3	2	1	3
1	3	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	2	1	3
1	3	2	2	1	3
1	2	2	2	1	2
1	3	3	3	1	2
2	3	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	3	1	4
1	3	3	3	1	3
2	4	4	4	1	3
1	2	3	3	0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	3	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	3	1	2
1	3	3	3	1	2
2	4	4	4	0	3
2	4	4	4	1	3
1	4	4	4	0	3
2	3	4	3	1	4
1	3	3	3	1	3
1	3	3	3	1	4
1	3	2	3	1	4
1	4	3	2	1	3
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3	4	4	4	0	3
2	2	2	2	0	3
3	4	4	4	0	3
1	3	2	2	0	2
2	3	4	4	0	3
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2	3	3	3	0	3
2	4	3	4	1	3
1	3	4	3	1	4
1	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	4	3	1	4
2	4	4	4	1	2
1	4	3	4	0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	3	3	2	1	2
2	4	4	4	0	2
1	2	2	2	0	2
3	4	4	4	0	3
2	2	2	2	0	2
1	3	3	3	1	2
1	2	2	2	1	2
2	3	3	3	0	3
1	2	2	2	1	2
1	3	3	3	0	3
2	3	3	3	1	3
1	3	3	4	1	4
1	1	1	1	1	1
2	3	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	3	1	3
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.150589862	0.3134769671	0.2914372493	-0.1776397589	-0.01820666928
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Negative Relationship	Negligible Relationship

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

I only drink coffee during special circumstances such as midterms or finals.	How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)?	How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?	How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?	Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?	How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila?
1	1	1	2	0	4
4	2	2	1	1	2
4	4	4	4	1	3
1	4	4	3	1	4
2	4	2	2	1	4
1	4	4	3	1	2
2	4	3	2	1	3
1	2	2	2	0	2
2	4	3	2	1	1
3	4	4	1	1	2
1	3	2	4	1	4
3	2	2	2	0	2
4	4	3	2	1	3
2	1	1	2	1	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	4	4	1	4
1	4	3	2	1	3
3	4	4	4	1	3
2	4	4	2	1	3
4	4	3	3	1	2
3	3	3	3	1	4
1	4	2	3	1	3
2	2	2	2	1	2
1	3	3	4	1	3
4	3	3	4	1	4
4	3	3	3	1	3
2	2	3	2	0	2
2	4	4	4	1	3
1	2	3	3	1	2
1	4	2	3	1	4
2	3	3	3	1	4
3	4	3	3	1	3
1	3	3	4	1	4
3	3	3	4	0	4
2	3	2	3	1	2
1	4	4	4	1	4
3	3	2	2	1	2
2	4	4	3	1	3
3	3	3	3	1	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	4	3	3	1	4
1	4	4	4	1	4
2	4	3	3	1	4
3	4	4	4	0	2
4	4	3	2	1	1
3	2	2	2	1	4
3	3	2	1	1	4
3	4	3	3	0	3
3	4	3	3	1	1
3	4	3	3	1	2
2	3	3	2	1	4
3	3	3	3	1	4
1	4	4	4	1	2
2	3	3	3	1	2
1	4	4	4	1	4
2	4	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	3	0	3
4	1	1	1	1	2
2	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	4	4	1	3
3	1	1	1	1	1
3	3	2	3	1	2
2	3	3	2	1	3
3	3	2	4	1	3
3	4	4	3	1	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	4	4	4	1	4
3	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	4	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	4	1	4
1	3	3	3	1	4
4	4	4	4	1	2
1	3	2	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	2	2	2	1	4
1	4	3	4	1	3
3	4	4	4	0	3
2	4	4	3	1	3
1	3	2	3	0	3
2	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	4	0	3
2	3	3	3	0	2
2	3	3	4	0	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	4	4	0	3
3	4	4	3	1	2
2	3	3	3	1	2
1	4	4	4	0	3
2	4	3	4	1	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

1	4	3	3	0	3
2	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	2	2	0	3
2	4	3	2	1	2
2	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	4	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	2
3	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	2
2	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	3	0	2
2	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	4	1	3
4	4	3	3	0	2
1	4	3	3	1	2
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	3	1	2
1	3	4	4	0	3
1	4	3	4	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	3	1	3
2	4	3	3	0	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	4	3	3	1	2
2	2	3	3	0	2
4	3	3	4	1	3
1	2	3	3	1	2
4	3	4	2	1	3
2	3	4	3	1	4
2	3	3	3	1	2
1	3	4	4	0	3
1	4	4	4	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	3
1	3	3	3	1	2
4	2	3	2	0	2
2	2	2	3	0	3
3	4	3	4	1	2
3	4	4	3	0	2
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	2	1	2
3	2	3	3	1	3
4	2	4	3	1	3
4	2	4	3	1	3
2	3	3	2	1	2
4	3	4	4	1	4
2	2	2	2	1	2
2	3	3	4	1	3
2	3	3	4	1	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	2	3	2	1	4
3	3	3	2	1	3
3	2	2	2	1	2
3	3	3	2	1	2
3	3	3	3	1	4
4	3	3	2	1	3
3	4	3	2	1	2
1	4	4	4	1	4
2	4	3	3	0	4
1	2	2	2	1	2
3	4	4	3	0	2
2	3	3	3	0	2
4	3	3	3	0	3
2	4	4	4	0	2
3	3	3	3	1	2
2	2	2	2	0	2
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	4
3	2	3	2	1	3
3	3	3	2	1	3
3	4	3	2	1	3
1	4	4	3	1	2
2	4	4	4	1	3
1	4	4	4	1	3
3	3	3	3	0	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	2	2	2	0	2
2	4	4	4	0	3
2	3	4	3	0	3
3	2	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	2	1	3
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	2	1	3
3	3	2	2	1	3
2	2	2	2	1	2
2	3	3	3	1	2
3	3	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	3	1	4
3	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	4	4	1	3
2	2	3	3	0	3
1	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	2
1	3	3	3	1	2
1	4	4	4	0	3
1	4	4	4	1	3
1	4	4	4	0	3
3	3	4	3	1	4
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	3	1	4
3	3	2	3	1	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	4	3	2	1	3
3	3	3	3	0	2
3	4	4	4	0	3
3	2	2	2	0	3
2	4	4	4	0	3
3	3	2	2	0	2
1	3	4	4	0	3
1	4	4	4	1	3
2	3	3	3	0	3
2	4	3	4	1	3
3	3	4	3	1	4
4	3	3	3	1	3
4	4	4	3	1	4
1	4	4	4	1	2
1	4	3	4	0	3
3	3	3	2	1	2
2	4	4	4	0	2
3	2	2	2	0	2
2	4	4	4	0	3
3	2	2	2	0	2
2	3	3	3	1	2
3	2	2	2	1	2
1	3	3	3	0	3
3	2	2	2	1	2
2	3	3	3	0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

	2	3	3	3	1	3
	2	3	3	4	1	4
	2	1	1	1	1	1
	2	3	3	3	1	3
	2	3	3	3	1	3
SPEARMA N'S CORRELAT ION	-0.237347 1606	-0.084746 59292	-0.315975 7754	0.05131233 038	-0.08952881 652	
MEANING	Weak Negative Relationshi p	Negligible Relationshi p	Weak Negative Relationshi p	Negligible Relationship	Negligible Relationship	

<p>I consume coffee more frequently than matcha.</p>	<p>How likely are you to support local coffee businesses near SSC-R Manila if they offer student deals (e.g., discounts, loyalty rewards)?</p>	<p>How likely are you to purchase coffee from businesses around SSC-R Manila?</p>	<p>How interested are you in having more coffee-related businesses near SSC-R Manila?</p>	<p>Do you believe that there are enough coffee shops around SSC-R Manila?</p>	<p>How much are you willing to pay for a cup of coffee around SSC-R Manila?</p>
1	1	1	2	0	4
3	2	2	1	1	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	4	4	1	3
4	4	4	3	1	4
4	4	2	2	1	4
4	4	4	3	1	2
3	4	3	2	1	3
1	2	2	2	0	2
3	4	3	2	1	1
4	4	4	1	1	2
1	3	2	4	1	4
3	2	2	2	0	2
1	4	3	2	1	3
3	1	1	2	1	2
4	3	3	3	1	3
4	4	4	4	1	4
3	4	3	2	1	3
3	4	4	4	1	3
4	4	4	2	1	3
4	4	3	3	1	2
1	3	3	3	1	4
4	4	2	3	1	3
3	2	2	2	1	2
4	3	3	4	1	3
2	3	3	4	1	4
4	3	3	3	1	3
3	2	3	2	0	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	4	4	1	3
4	2	3	3	1	2
3	4	2	3	1	4
4	3	3	3	1	4
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	4	1	4
2	3	3	4	0	4
2	3	2	3	1	2
4	4	4	4	1	4
3	3	2	2	1	2
4	4	4	3	1	3
3	3	3	3	1	3
1	4	3	3	1	4
2	4	4	4	1	4
4	4	3	3	1	4
2	4	4	4	0	2
4	4	3	2	1	1
2	2	2	2	1	4
2	3	2	1	1	4
2	4	3	3	0	3
3	4	3	3	1	1
4	4	3	3	1	2
2	3	3	2	1	4
3	3	3	3	1	4
4	4	4	4	1	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	3	3	3	1	2
4	4	4	4	1	4
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	3	0	3
4	1	1	1	1	2
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	4	4	4	1	3
1	1	1	1	1	1
3	3	2	3	1	2
4	3	3	2	1	3
4	3	2	4	1	3
3	4	4	3	1	4
3	4	4	4	1	4
3	4	3	3	1	3
4	4	3	3	1	3
4	4	3	4	1	2
4	4	3	3	1	3
4	4	3	4	1	4
3	3	3	3	1	4
4	4	4	4	1	2
3	3	2	3	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	2	2	2	1	4
3	4	3	4	1	3
1	4	4	4	0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

4	4	4	3	1	3
3	3	2	3	0	3
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	4	0	3
2	3	3	3	0	2
3	3	3	4	0	2
3	4	3	3	1	3
4	4	4	4	0	3
3	4	4	3	1	2
3	3	3	3	1	2
2	4	4	4	0	3
3	4	3	4	1	2
3	4	3	3	0	3
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	2	2	0	3
2	4	3	2	1	2
3	4	3	3	1	2
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	4	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	2
3	4	3	3	1	2
3	4	3	3	1	2
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	3	0	2

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	4	3	3	1	2
3	4	3	4	1	3
4	4	3	3	0	2
4	4	3	3	1	2
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	3	1	2
3	3	4	4	0	3
4	4	3	4	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	3	0	2
4	4	3	3	1	2
4	2	3	3	0	2
1	3	3	4	1	3
4	2	3	3	1	2
4	3	4	2	1	3
2	3	4	3	1	4
3	3	3	3	1	2
4	3	4	4	0	3
4	4	4	4	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	3
4	3	3	3	1	2
3	2	3	2	0	2
4	2	2	3	0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

2	4	3	4	1	2
3	4	4	3	0	2
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	2	1	2
4	2	3	3	1	3
3	2	4	3	1	3
3	2	4	3	1	3
2	3	3	2	1	2
3	3	4	4	1	4
3	2	2	2	1	2
3	3	3	4	1	3
3	3	3	4	1	2
3	2	3	2	1	4
3	3	3	2	1	3
3	2	2	2	1	2
3	3	3	2	1	2
4	3	3	3	1	4
4	3	3	2	1	3
3	4	3	2	1	2
4	4	4	4	1	4
3	4	3	3	0	4
1	2	2	2	1	2
3	4	4	3	0	2
3	3	3	3	0	2
4	3	3	3	0	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	4	4	4	0	2
1	3	3	3	1	2
2	2	2	2	0	2
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	3	1	4
3	2	3	2	1	3
3	3	3	2	1	3
3	4	3	2	1	3
4	4	4	3	1	2
4	4	4	4	1	3
4	4	4	4	1	3
2	3	3	3	0	2
2	2	2	2	0	2
2	4	4	4	0	3
3	3	4	3	0	3
3	2	3	3	1	3
3	4	3	2	1	3
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	2	1	3
3	2	2	2	1	2
3	3	3	3	1	2
3	3	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	3	1	4
3	3	3	3	1	3

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	4	4	4	1	3
4	2	3	3	0	3
4	3	3	3	1	3
4	4	3	3	1	2
4	3	3	3	1	2
4	4	4	4	0	3
3	4	4	4	1	3
3	4	4	4	0	3
4	3	4	3	1	4
4	3	3	3	1	3
4	3	3	3	1	4
4	3	2	3	1	4
3	4	3	2	1	3
3	3	3	3	0	2
3	4	4	4	0	3
2	2	2	2	0	3
3	4	4	4	0	3
2	3	2	2	0	2
4	3	4	4	0	3
3	4	4	4	1	3
3	3	3	3	0	3
4	4	3	4	1	3
3	3	4	3	1	4
4	3	3	3	1	3
3	4	4	3	1	4

San Sebastian College – Recoletos, Manila

3	4	4	4	1	2
3	4	3	4	0	3
2	3	3	2	1	2
3	4	4	4	0	2
2	2	2	2	0	2
3	4	4	4	0	3
3	2	2	2	0	2
2	3	3	3	1	2
3	2	2	2	1	2
3	3	3	3	0	3
3	2	2	2	1	2
3	3	3	3	0	3
2	3	3	3	1	3
3	3	3	4	1	4
2	1	1	1	1	1
3	3	3	3	1	3
2	3	3	3	1	3
SPEARMAN'S CORRELATION	0.2233269891	0.2789763668	0.1835334089	0.1654038212	0.0517613299
MEANING	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Weak Positive Relationship	Negligible Relationship